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**The Second Nagorno-Karabakh War: A Multimodal Critical
Discourse Analysis of Social Media Posts of President
Ilham Aliyev and Prime Minister Nikol Pashinyan**

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This research is dedicated to all those affected by the Second Nagorno-Karabakh War—those who lost their lives, those who continue to bear the scars of the conflict, and the countless individuals and families whose lives have been forever altered. May this research serve as a small step toward understanding the power of communication in shaping our world, and as a reminder of the urgent need for peace, healing, and reconciliation in regions torn apart by war. Finally, to the youth of Armenia and Azerbaijan, who carry the burden of this history, I hope for a future where dialogue, empathy, and peace prevails.

Abstract

This interdisciplinary study explores the strategic communication and information warfare employed by President Ilham Aliyev of Azerbaijan and Prime Minister Nikol Pashinyan of Armenia during the Second Nagorno-Karabakh War. By analysing their Facebook posts through Multimodal Critical Discourse Analysis, this research examines how social media was weaponised to shape public perception, amplify nationalistic ideologies, and demoralise the opposing side. The study incorporates insights from interviews with young people from both countries, revealing how the war discourse resonated with youth and shaped their views on the conflict. Findings suggest that both leaders used social media to advance their national objectives, but with contrasting approaches. Aliyev's posts centred on military victories and territorial claims sought to demoralise the opposing side, while Pashinyan's rhetoric evoked national sacrifice and historical resilience whilst protecting the entire extent of losses. Despite their differing approaches, both leaders' social media content deepened polarisation and hindered peace efforts. Additionally, it highlights the role of emotional stress caused by the war's discourse and the effect of incidental news consumption, particularly among youth who are prolific social media users.

This study contributes to the growing body of literature on strategic communication, information warfare, and social media in modern conflicts, demonstrating the evolving role of digital platforms in shaping conflict narratives. The findings underscore the need for enhanced media literacy and the regulation of social media algorithms to prevent the amplification of divisive rhetoric in future conflicts.

Keywords: Second Nagorno-Karabakh War, Strategic Communication, Information Warfare, Facebook, Aliyev, Pashinyan

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List of Abbreviations

- **CL** Critical Linguistics
- **CDA** Critical Discourse Analysis
- **CDS** Critical Discourse Studies
- **DoD** Department of Defence
- **EU** European Union
- **Fig** Figure
- **IDF** Israel Defence Forces
- **INGO** International Non-Governmental Organization
- **IO** Information Operations
- **IW** Information Warfare
- **MCDA** Multimodal Critical Discourse Analysis
- **MISO** Military Information Support Operations
- **MoD** Ministry of Defence
- **MoFA** Ministry of Foreign Affairs
- **NATO** North Atlantic Treaty Organisation
- **NGO** Non-Governmental Organization
- **NSAs** Non-State Actors
- **OSCE** Organisation for Security and Co-operation in Europe
- **PDA** Political Discourse Analysis
- **PR** Public Relations
- **StratCom** Strategic Communication
- **VPN** Virtual Private Network

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1.0 Introduction

Throughout history, the power of communication and the ability of leaders to convey messages effectively have significantly shaped the outcomes of conflicts. Pope Urban II's address at Clermont convinced thousands to travel across continents, prepared to give their lives in a place they had never seen before (Field, 2013). Another salient example is Winston Churchill's famous "We shall fight on the beaches" speech delivered in 1940, which became iconic for inspiring courage and determination among the British public and Armed Forces during a time of defeat, fear, and uncertainty (Israel, 2013). His clear, resolute communication helped maintain morale and motivated the British people to persevere despite intense bombings and hardships. Beyond rallying his nation, Churchill's speeches played a key role in securing support from the United States—ultimately a crucial factor in the Allied victory during the Second World War (ibid). In today's digital age, this communicative power remains potent. Modern leaders frequently utilise social media platforms to direct national narratives and influence both domestic and international audiences, echoing the same principles of shaping public perception once exercised in more traditional forums.

In the same vein, this dissertation examines the role of communication in shaping narratives surrounding the Second Nagorno-Karabakh War, a conflict fought in the South Caucasus from 27 September to 10 November 2020 between Armenia and Azerbaijan. By focusing on the social media posts of President Ilham Aliyev of Azerbaijan and Prime Minister Nikol Pashinyan of Armenia, this research explores how strategic communication (StratCom) and information warfare (IW) are deployed in modern conflicts. The interdisciplinary nature of this work situates it within the fields of StratCom, conflict communication, and social media studies, emphasising how

contemporary wars are waged not only on the battlefield but also through carefully crafted narratives disseminated via digital platforms.

StratCom in conflict refers to the deliberate and coordinated use of communication activities by state and non-state actors to influence public opinion, shape narratives, and achieve specific political or military objectives (Paul, 2011; Cornish, Lindley-French & Yorke, 2011). It involves integrating various tools—such as social media, diplomacy, psychological operations, and IW—to control perceptions, manage crises, and sustain support for either war efforts or peacebuilding initiatives. By ensuring that messages align with broader strategic goals, StratCom significantly impacts the conduct of modern conflicts, both on the battlefield and in the informational domain. Against this backdrop, the Second Nagorno-Karabakh War offers a revealing case study of how leaders employ StratCom and IW. This research specifically investigates how President Aliyev and Prime Minister Pashinyan used Facebook to shape national and international perceptions, bolster morale, and assert political legitimacy. To achieve this, the study employs Multimodal Critical Discourse Analysis (MCDA), complemented by ethnographic insights. First, the leaders' Facebook posts are translated (where required) and analysed; then, the opinions of young people from both countries are gathered. Given that youth are prolific users of social media (Kemp, 2023), understanding their perspectives is central to examining how such platforms can influence—and potentially intensify—conflicts. These insights aim to inform policy recommendations intended to strengthen social media regulation, encourage peace, and foster reconciliation in post-conflict societies.

The setting of this research is the Second Nagorno-Karabakh War, a conflict deeply rooted in decades of territorial disputes between Armenia and Azerbaijan. National narratives surrounding the war were shaped by historical, cultural, and political factors,

with each side employing varied communication tactics to assert their legitimacy and rally national support. The war itself was not only fought on the battlefield but also in the digital sphere, where both Aliyev and Pashinyan sought to engage their populations and the wider international community through social media (Giles and Bhat 2020).

An utmost effort has been made to keep the study unbiased and avoid taking sides with any of the involved belligerents that shall be discussed at length in the methodology section. This study also acknowledges that the conflict is known by different names in both countries, i.e., the Second Artsakh War in Armenia and the Second Karabakh War in Azerbaijan. However, the widely used international term, the Second Nagorno-Karabakh War, has been adopted here to maintain impartiality (United Nations 2020). Likewise, both President Ilham Aliyev of Azerbaijan (@PresidentIlhamAliyev) and Prime Minister Nikol Pashinyan of Armenia (@nikol.pashinyan) operated Facebook pages under their personal names, not official titles. It is understood that these accounts are often managed by teams, with posts made on their behalf. For instance, President Aliyev's posts frequently feature the Office of the President of Azerbaijan's logo. However, the personal touch remains, making it hard for to distinguish between personal and official discourse. Therefore, it is important to note that posts of Ilham Aliyev or Nikol Pashinyan in this research may have been crafted by their respective communication teams. Nonetheless, the posts still carry their authority, blending personal and institutional voices in a way that amplifies their impact.

In analysing the social media posts during this conflict, this research contributes to evolving role of StratCom, IW, and social media in contemporary conflicts, illustrating how these tools shape the outcomes of wars not only through military action but also

via informational control and narrative manipulation. In doing so, it underscores the significant impact of digital platforms in influencing both domestic and international audiences, opening pathways for more nuanced understanding of social media's role in conflict escalation and resolution.

1.1 Aim

The aim of this study is to conduct MCDA of the selected Facebook posts of President Ilham Aliyev of Azerbaijan and Prime Minister Nikol Pashinyan of Armenia during the Second Nagorno-Karabakh War.

1.2 Scope

The scope is limited to Facebook posts due to its widespread popularity in both the countries, the diversity of the content that can be posted on it (including text, images, and videos), and its unrestricted accessibility during the war despite internet restrictions, which makes it an ideal platform for capturing a snapshot of social media war discourse. The period for this study is confined to the duration of the war.

2.0 Literature Review

This chapter outlines the research by reviewing existing literature and establishing the study's theoretical framework. In this regard, this chapter first introduces the interplay of StratCom, IW, and social media. It then examines key theoretical perspectives—including critical discourse analysis (CDA) and multimodal critical discourse analysis (MCDA)—and concludes by discussing the Second Nagorno-Karabakh War's unique geopolitical dimensions. It also briefly examines the role of social media as an alternative to traditional news media for younger generations, its influence on conflicts, particularly as a platform for StratCom and IW.

2.1 The New Troika: StratCom, IW and Social Media

StratCom, IW, and social media have emerged as a powerful “troika” (Russian for three) in modern political contestation, reshaping how actors influence public opinion and electoral outcomes. In this context, troika refers to a synergistic combination of three key elements working in concert to achieve a common goal, much like the traditional Russian vehicle pulled by three horses. StratCom plays a pivotal role in crafting persuasive narratives that resonate with specific audiences, often utilising data-driven insights to refine messaging (Borah and Xiao, 2018). Concurrently, IW leverages these narratives by exploiting vulnerabilities in information systems, disseminating disinformation, and amplifying certain discourses to create confusion or division among the public (Pamment, 2020). Social media platforms serve as the battleground where these tactics unfold, providing a vast, unregulated space for rapid dissemination and engagement with diverse audiences. This dynamic has enabled political actors to bypass traditional media gatekeepers, directly target constituents, and rapidly respond to opponents, thereby significantly altering the landscape of political communication (Howard and Kollanyi, 2016). This ‘troika’ is particularly

relevant within public relations and political communication fields, as it underscores how tailored messaging (StratCom), manipulative tactics (IW), and interactive platforms (social media) converge to shape public perceptions. The confluence of these elements has led to a new era of political contestation, where the speed, reach, and impact of StratCom and IW are exponentially magnified through social media channels.

2.1.1 StratCom and its Role in Conflicts

States have always grappled with managing the flow of information during wartime. The impact of state communication on this flow has consistently played an important role in determining the outcome of conflicts (Jungblut, 2020). Practitioners in the field generally term this umbrella of communication activities under StratCom but is it any different from PR or other related disciplines? According to Falkheimer and Heide (2018), StratCom integrates PR, organisational communication, and marketing communication—which have historically been distinct fields—into a cohesive framework, recognising the interconnectedness of internal and external communication. This integration allows organizations to address communication holistically, enhancing overall effectiveness and coherence. StratCom is often viewed from a post-positivist paradigm, wherein like PR StratCom is viewed through empirical, measurable outcomes, but StratCom especially in security context prioritises clear, mission-oriented communication strategies to achieve security and policy objectives (Cornelissen, 2020). This has rendered StratCom to be the go-to word used in government and military spheres. However, critics from the critical paradigm (see Curtin, 2012, pp. 36 for communication paradigms) scrutinise StratCom for its role in propaganda and influence operations (Snow, 2010), like PR in the corporate was

critiqued for perpetuating corporate hegemony and manipulating public opinion (Moloney, 2006).

Nonetheless, StratCom is used widely in both government, security, academic and corporate circles and it can mean different things to different people (Falkheimer and Heide, 2018). For instance, scholars in the field like Hallahan et al. contributing to International Journal of StratCom define it as "the purposeful use of communication by an organization to fulfil its mission" (2007, pp. 3) whilst this is in contrast to Paul, a senior social scientist at RAND (whose work has influenced US defence policy), who views it as "coordinated actions, messages, images, and other forms of signalling or engagement intended to inform influence, persuade, selected audiences in support of national objectives" (2011, pp. 3). Paul argues that StratCom involves whole of government approach and in pursuit of national objectives, coordinated at the highest level and dished out to all branches of the government both civilian and military and cannot be executed in isolation at the level of individual organisations. Likewise, governments have their own definitions suiting their objectives and policy interests. NATO defines it as " the planned and integrated process of delivering messages and information to support its objectives and missions," emphasizing coherence and alignment in messaging to achieve strategic goals and maintain operational effectiveness (NATO Strategic Communications Centre of Excellence 2021). The US DoD has a similar understanding of StratCom as "the coordinated and synchronised use of actions, messages, and communications resources to advance national interests and support policy objectives", focusing on integrating communication strategies with national security aims and ensuring consistency across various channels and agencies (Department of Defence, 2020). Meanwhile, the Russian approach to StratCom is different as it centres on IW and strategic influence, using

information to shape perceptions and advance national objectives (Russian Ministry of Defence, 2019). Furthermore, this contrast between government, think tanks versus scholars continues upon reviewing the latest research handbook on StratCom (Falkheimer and Heide, 2022). It is safe to conclude that whilst definitions of government/security organisations, scholars, and corporate overlap on fundamental concepts of StratCom, each exists in its own space with its own distinct lexicon.

Although scholars frequently cite “misinformation,” “disinformation,” and “propaganda” within discussions of StratCom, these terms have nuanced distinctions. **Misinformation** generally refers to unintentional inaccuracies or falsehoods spread without malice (Wardle and Derakhshan, 2017). **Disinformation**, by contrast, involves deliberately fabricated or manipulated information designed to deceive (Pamment, 2020). **Propaganda** is broader still, typically encompassing orchestrated campaigns to shape perceptions or actions in ways that serve a particular agenda (Snow, 2010). In conflict settings, such propagandistic efforts can become integral to state or non-state actor strategies, blurring lines between information sharing, deception, and persuasion.

StratCom plays a pivotal role in all conflicts today, shaping public perception, supporting policy objectives, and profoundly impacting the success of military operations. This is echoed by Falkheimer and Heide (2022), who argue that StratCom is essential for managing the narratives that drive public and political support. Additionally, Cornish, Lindley-French, and Yorke (2011) highlight that in the modern information environment, the battle for hearts and minds is as critical as the physical confrontation on the ground. The integration of StratCom into military strategy ensures coherence between actions and messages, enhancing legitimacy and undermining adversarial propaganda (Paul, 2011). Consequently, the importance of StratCom in

contemporary conflicts cannot be overstated, as it serves as a force multiplier that bridges the gap between tactical ground operations and strategic objectives. This is essentially true for Russia which employed sophisticated propaganda and disinformation campaigns in support of its military operations in its success in Crimea (Thornton, 2015) and Syria (White, 2018). Research shows that US and NATO have remained more reactionary in their StratCom efforts and have had mixed success, case in point hearts and minds campaign in Iraq (Kilcullen, 2009) and countering Taliban narrative in Afghanistan (Corman, Trethewey, and Goodall, 2008).

2.1.2 Rise of Social Media and Youth

Social media has transformed the landscape of StratCom, especially in how governments disseminate information and shape public opinion. Unlike traditional media, which operates in regulated, one-way environments controlled by gatekeepers (Farwell, 2020), social media allows for multidirectional communication with minimal oversight. These platforms provide governments with direct access to citizens, enabling them to bypass traditional media and deliver targeted messages to specific demographics (Graham, 2014). This approach has been successful in contexts ranging from political campaigns to public health initiatives.

However, the dominance of social media also presents challenges, particularly for younger users who increasingly rely on these platforms for news. Studies indicate that nearly 90% of Millennials and Generation Z consume news on platforms like Facebook, X, Telegram, and Instagram (Pew Research Centre, 2020). Swart (2021) notes that although these users are often digitally savvy, their news literacy skills may not be robust enough to scrutinise the legitimacy of content they encounter. This challenge is amplified by the “incidental” nature of social media news consumption, where sensationalist or misleading content may go viral without traditional editorial

checks (Boczkowski et al., 2018). Thus, the risk of misinformation, disinformation, and even overt propaganda escalates, particularly when social media algorithms reward high engagement over accuracy. A notable example is the Russian government's alleged use of social media to sway public opinion during the 2016 U.S. elections (Howard et al., 2019).

Studies underscore how government communication via social media can significantly influence young people (Edelman Trust Barometer, 2020). Guess, Nyhan, and Reifler (2020) further show that exposure to state-backed misinformation shapes the political views of younger cohorts, emphasising the need for stronger critical media literacy. In effect, the very platforms that enable more open discourse can also magnify manipulative tactics, posing both opportunities and hazards for StratCom in conflict scenarios.

2.1.3 Warfare in the 21st Century

The classical definition of war, often traced to Clausewitz, remains foundational in military theory. His work, *On War* (1832), described war as “a continuation of policy through violent means,” encapsulated in his famous trinity: violence, chance, and political objectives (Clausewitz 1832 cited in Echevarria II, 2007, pp. 69). Clausewitz's theory, shaped by the Westphalian state system, dominated military thought until the nuclear and information age. Critics argue that Clausewitz overlooks deeper cultural and psychological drivers of war. Gat (2006) points out that Clausewitz neglects cultural factors, while Keegan (1993) asserts that war taps into deep human emotions, with communities often fighting for reasons beyond political motives, such as religion or tribal loyalty. Similarly, van Creveld (2008) highlights the psychological dimension of war, describing it as a source of profound joy, excitement, and a test of manhood, values often driving participation in conflict.

Despite these critiques, Clausewitz's principles still hold relevance today. Kilcullen (2013) and Lonsdale (2004) argue that even in the information age, Clausewitz's trinity remains valid. Organised violence for political ends continues to define conflicts, whether waged by states or NSAs. The introduction of nuclear weapons and cyberspace has added new dimensions to warfare, but the fundamental nature of war, as Clausewitz articulated, remains consistent. His trinity—violence, chance, and political objectives—continues to serve as a useful model for understanding both historical and contemporary conflicts. In the context of **information warfare**, Clausewitz's framework translates into new domains where "policy" is pursued via strategic messaging, cyberattacks, and the shaping of narratives (Theohary, 2015). The psychological impact—once limited to propaganda leaflets or radio broadcasts—now extends to real-time social media feeds, shifting how belligerents attempt to gain advantage both on and off the battlefield.

2.1.4 Cyber Space: The New Realm of Warfare

In contrast to traditional battlefields of land, sea, air, and space, cyberspace is a human-created domain that largely exists beyond physical boundaries. Originally a term from science fiction (Gibson, 2013), it has now become a key arena for conflict. According to Britannica, cyberspace is a virtual domain formed by the complex interconnections of computers, servers, routers, and other digital components (Bussell, 2023). Western think tanks and powers like the USA, UK, and the EU generally agree on this definition (Tabansky, 2011; Congressional Research Service, 2023; HM Government 2009; European Union Agency for Cybersecurity, 2023). However, significant differences exist between western, Russian, and Chinese views on cyberspace. According to Giles and Hagestad (2013), the west sees cyberspace as a distinct domain within a broader information environment, focusing on networked

IT infrastructures. In contrast, Russia and China view cyberspace as inseparable from the wider concept of information space, which includes broader activities beyond networked systems. Control and governance also differ between these perspectives. Western nations advocate for an open and free cyberspace, emphasising international principles and human rights. Conversely, Russia and China maintain strict control over their information spaces, considering it essential for state security and sovereignty. Libicki (2009) describes cyberspace as consisting of three layers: the “physical” layer (infrastructure like circuits and communication systems), the “software” layer (programming controlling physical components), and the “data” layer (stored information). Consequently, IW has emerged as one of the methods to wage war within information and cyberspace (Taddeo ,2016).

The advent of IW marks a significant shift in warfare, comparable to historical milestones such as the invention of gunpowder, the industrial revolution, and atomic weapons (Farwell, 2020). While IW has always existed, the rise of social media and the internet has significantly expanded its reach and complexity, demanding a deeper understanding (Theohary, 2015). Technological advancements have intensified IW, making it a key element in modern conflicts, referred to by many as the latest "revolution in military affairs" (Arquilla and Ronfeldt, 1997; Taddeo, 2020).

In IW, information serves as both the weapon and the target. According to Bakshi, it is a “method to impose national will on an adversary, maintaining apparent anonymity without violating international laws on the sovereignty of other nations” (2018, pp. 178). The concept of IW dates to Edward Waltz's seminal work in 1998, later developed by US military doctrine, broadening its scope from military-focused IW to the wider concept of IOs, with both civilian and military applications (Bakshi, 2018). Kuehl (2002, pp. 36) defines IO as “Actions taken to affect adversary information and

information systems while defending one's own," while IW refers to "Information operations conducted during crises or conflicts to achieve specific objectives against specific adversaries." Kuehl argues that both IW and IO involve controlling and exploiting the information environment across the conflict spectrum, using various government agencies (Kuehl, 2002). IW and IO are similar as both involve using information to influence perceptions and outcomes in conflict; this study will thus group them together because they operate in tandem.

IW can be divided into technical operations, targeting machines, and psychological operations, targeting people (Waltzman, 2017). Bakshi (2018) identifies five core components of IW: Electronic Warfare, Computer Network Operations, Psychological Operations (now renamed MISO), Military Deception, and Operations Security. The relationship of StratCom and IW is best explained by US Armed Forces, i.e. StratCom involves a concentrated US government effort to engage key audiences and foster conditions favourable to US interests through coordinated messages and actions. MISO support StratCom by influencing foreign audiences to achieve US objectives (US Joint Chiefs of Staff, 2011), thereby extending it purely beyond military application, emphasising human cognitive abilities as the target. One could argue that goal of IW is to influence the human mind by manipulating various forms of communication. Conversely, Russia views IW/IO as a continuous strategic activity, perceiving itself in a constant state of IW, unlike the West (Waltzman, 2017).

Social media companies now recognise this reality. Facebook's 2017 admission that "overt information operations" took place on its platform during the 2016 U.S. election (Weedon et al., 2017) underscores how governments, militaries, terror organisations, and non-state actors exploit the digital domain to achieve tactical or

strategic aims. The low cost and relatively high anonymity of social media make it a particularly fertile ground for IW.

2.2 Overview of Second Nagorno-Karabakh War Literature

Existing research on the Second Nagorno-Karabakh War primarily addresses geopolitical and historical dimensions, often from either pro-Armenian, pro-Azerbaijani, or neutral standpoints. While some scholars analyse social media's role—especially Telegram (Rostomyan, 2023)—and examine IW or propaganda (Erofeeva and Tolstokulakova, 2021; Hakobyan, 2021), there remains a notable gap in comparative studies focusing on how the conflict's heads of state (rather than ministries or spokespersons) leveraged social media for war-related messaging. Kopečný (2021) looked at the Ministry of Foreign Affairs (MoFA) and Ministry of Defence (MoD) communications, but no parallel research has systematically analysed the Facebook posts of President Aliyev and Prime Minister Pashinyan. Consequently, this study fills a crucial gap by concentrating on their communications and younger audiences' perceptions, with only minimal background context provided to situate the broader conflict.

2.2.1 Background

The conflict between Armenia and Azerbaijan in the South Caucasus has festered for over three decades, rooted in the post-Soviet struggle over the region of Nagorno-Karabakh. According to Yavuz and Gunter (2022) this territory, although internationally recognized as part of Azerbaijan (following independence from USSR), had a predominantly ethnic Armenian composition. Following Armenia's victory in the First Nagorno-Karabakh War in 1994, the region declared itself as the semi-autonomous Republic of Artsakh under Armenian support (Welt and Bowen, 2021). Therefore, the region in almost all official Armenian discourse is usually referred to as Artsakh. According to Yavuz and Gunter (2022), this conflict typifies the perennial clash of human rights charters of right to self-determination (advocated by Armenia for majority ethnic Armenians), and territorial integrity (de jure part of Azerbaijan). Additionally, it underscores the long-term conflicts that arise when receding world powers create borders without considering the ethnic and demographic realities on the ground.

Fig 1&2 Prepared for U.S. Congress, Maps showing territorial changes (Welt and Bowen 2021, p.10-12)

2.2.2 The Second Nagorno-Karabakh War

The region saw intermittent skirmishes after the first war, but the conflict reignited on 27th September 2020, when Azerbaijan launched an operation to reclaim the territory, leading to a 44-day war with heavy casualties and widespread displacement on both sides (Askerov and Ibadoghlu, 2022). Independent observers noted that Türkiye provided extensive support to Azerbaijan (Jones, 2020), though Armenia also accused Azerbaijan of using Syrian mercenaries, a claim Azerbaijan denied (Cookman, 2020). Despite multiple ceasefire attempts, Azerbaijan made significant gains, including the capture of Shusha/Shushi (Azerbaijani/Armenian pronunciation), a city of psychological importance, on 8th November. The war ended with Armenia's signing of ceasefire agreement on 10 November, after Prime Minister Pashinyan addressed the nation on Facebook Live, explaining his reasons (Hedenskog et al., 2020). Russia brokered the ceasefire, which involved territorial concessions to Azerbaijan and the deployment of Russian peacekeepers (Welt and Bowen, 2021). Azerbaijan's success, reclaiming over 70% of the territory, eventually led to its full control of the region by September 2023, with most ethnic Armenians fleeing to Armenia (BBC News, 2023). The war was characterized by a pervasive digital media landscape, marked by extensive misinformation, IW and propaganda (Mirovalev, 2020). According to Mamadaliev (2021), both Armenian and Azerbaijani officials engaged in widespread propaganda, including demonising the enemy, promoting military successes, and encouraging patriotic sentiment. Armenian statements were noted to be more restrained, likely due to the unfavourable situation on the ground, while Azerbaijani messages were more frequent. Both sides also employed online activists to control social media narratives, with significant participation from the Armenian diaspora, termed "transnational cyber warriors" by Chernobrov (2022). Local media mainly relied

on official government sources (ERMES III, 2020), with Azerbaijani President and the MoD sharing videos of destroyed Armenian equipment, city captures, and drone footages (Hakobyan, 2021).

Social media became the main channel for information dissemination, with both sides resorting to restrict open internet usage. Azerbaijan imposed severe restrictions, whilst Armenia also restricted certain social media applications to prevent live reporting of troop movements (Freedom House, 2020). Despite these restrictions, VPNs became widely used in both countries to access blocked applications, with Telegram and WhatsApp emerging as key platforms for unofficial, unmoderated news groups (Rostomyan, 2023). This war highlighted a shift in information dissemination from the first war, with quicker, more digital information spread.

2.2.3 President Ilham Aliyev's Digital Communication

A key aspect of President Ilham Aliyev's strategy was his emphasis on X (formerly Twitter), despite its relative unpopularity in Azerbaijan at the time. However, the same content was shared across major platforms, including Facebook and Instagram, and tailored for legacy media. According to Parker (2020), this marked a shift from traditional, formal PR to more informal, high-production videos, demonstrating an understanding of platform-specific engagement. Critics such as Sahakyan (2023) accuse Aliyev of dehumanising Armenians in wartime speeches, a charge echoed by Turkish scholars Kösen and Erdoğan (2023). However, these works did not investigate how ordinary citizens—especially younger demographics—perceive or respond to this discourse.

2.2.4 Armenian Prime Minister Nikol Pashinyan's Digital Communication

Armenian Prime Minister Nikol Pashinyan had more followers on his digital platforms than Azerbaijan's President and was praised for his effective use of social media since his rise to power during the 2018 democratic revolution (Parker, 2020). However, several analysts (Parker, 2020; Reynolds, 2021) suggest that Pashinyan's fragmented and less coordinated approach during the war was less effective in controlling the narrative and countering Azerbaijani claims. This undermined Armenia's credibility and allowed Azerbaijan to dominate the discourse, creating an environment where misinformation thrived and weakened Armenia's position in the conflict.

During the war, new figures like press secretary Colonel Artsrun Hovhannisyan and spokesperson Major Shushan Stepanyan, both from MoD, emerged as key sources of information in Armenia. They conducted communications through their personal and official social media accounts and quickly became household names (Hakobyan, 2021). While this provided direct communication, it limited the broader reach of the Prime Minister's platform.

2.3 Theoretical Concepts of CDA/ CDS and MCDA

CDA is a multidisciplinary methodology rooted in critical theory, drawing on the foundational works of Antonio Gramsci, Louis Althusser, and scholars from the Frankfurt School (Wodak and Meyer, 2009). Gramsci's concept of cultural hegemony plays a key role in CDA, examining how dominant groups maintain power through ideological means (Fairclough, 2010). Althusser's notion of ideological state apparatuses provides a framework for understanding how discourse operates within societal structures, reinforcing dominant ideologies (Althusser, 1971; van Dijk, 2008). The critical theory tradition of the Frankfurt School, particularly the works of Adorno and Horkheimer, also informs CDA's theoretical foundations, emphasising the critique of cultural and ideological dimensions in capitalist societies (Wodak, 2011; Habermas,

1987). CDA also incorporates critical linguistic theory and Michel Foucault's discourse theory (Regmi, 2017). It has evolved from CL into what is now often referred to as CDS (Flowerdew and Richardson, 2017). This shift was partly due to misconceptions that CDA was a single method within discourse analysis. To clarify this and highlight the diversity of methodologies, the term CDS has gained preference (Van Dijk, 2015). There are roughly seven well-known approaches within CDA/CDS, commonly used in research, publications, and journals (see Catalano and Waugh 2020, pp. 155-217). Despite the diversity of these methodologies, there is broad agreement on CDA's core tenets (Van Dijk, 2001: 2015). This research focuses on Van Dijk's definition of CDA, described as "discourse analytical research that primarily studies the way social-power abuse and inequality are enacted, reproduced, legitimated, and resisted by text and talk in the social and political context" (Van Dijk, 2015, pp. 466). After reviewing contemporary studies and critiques, a specific theoretical approach within CDA/CDS has been chosen.

2.3.1 Criticism of CDA

Despite its contributions, CDA/CDS has been critiqued for focusing on language while neglecting other semiotic resources and for its inherent subjectivity in discourse analysis (Blommaert, 2005). Breeze (2011) reviewing CDA/CDS research practice highlights that it is critiqued for methodological inconsistencies, theoretical ambiguities, and the potential orthodoxy it has developed, which may undermine its reflexive goals. For instance, explicit political commitments may influence analysis, and its reliance on diverse and sometimes conflicting theories can create theoretical confusion. In response, scholars stress the need for reflexivity and self-critique, arguing these practices are vital for the field's growth (Catalano and Waugh, 2020, pp. 96). Methodologically, it has been criticised for "impressionistic" text analysis and for

moving too quickly from data analysis to social theory, potentially leading to weak conclusions (Breeze, 2011, pp. 520-521). Similarly, its focus on negative discourse and power imbalances has been seen as overly deterministic, overlooking the potential for positive social change (ibid). In response, Catalano and Waugh suggest that this criticism led to the development of Positive Discourse Analysis, which focuses on how discourse can inspire positive societal change (2020, pp. 232-234). Additionally, CDA has been criticised for not adequately addressing the relationship between texts and their social contexts, often neglecting audience reception (Breeze, 2011, pp. 521). In response, Machin and Mayr (2023) propose a more ethnographic approach that considers how texts are interpreted by their intended publics rather than solely by analysts (2023, pp. 321).

2.3.2 Review of Comparative Studies Using CDA/CDS Framework

CDA/CDS has been widely applied to analyse speeches, war discourse, and campaigns of powerful figures, often focusing on “the language of those in power, responsible for inequalities” (Wodak and Meyer, 2009, pp. 9). A review of comparative research highlights key methodologies used in CDA/CDS studies.

Solopova and Naumova (2024) examined "just war" rhetoric in speeches by U.S. Presidents Obama and Biden, using van Dijk's socio-cognitive approach to compare how they justified military interventions in Syria and Ukraine. While their analysis uncovered underlying socio-cognitive representations, it could have been strengthened by exploring public reception and rhetoric effectiveness. Incorporating social semiotics would have also deepened the understanding of how visual and symbolic elements contributed to the conveyed ideologies.

Similarly, Pal (2017) used Fairclough's CDA framework to analyse Narendra Modi's speeches, focusing on how his language framed themes like corruption to connect

with the masses. Mohammadi and Javadi (2017) also employed Fairclough's CDA model, alongside van Dijk's ideological discourse analysis, to Trump's 2016 election acceptance speech, examining the experiential, relational, and expressive values of his language. Both studies, however, could have further explored how these rhetorical strategies influenced political outcomes, public perception, and the media's role in amplifying or challenging the discourse.

A notable study by Şeşen et al. (2022) applied PDA to Azerbaijani President Aliyev's speeches during the Second Nagorno-Karabakh War, analysing six televised speeches using Ponton's analytical model. This model considered context, camera angles, tone, body language, and rhetorical devices. The study demonstrated how Aliyev used ethos and pathos to build a self-confident, authoritative image and to evoke emotions like sadness and hope, and later pride as the war favoured Azerbaijan (ibid, pp. 1743-1747). While the study effectively illustrated Aliyev's image construction, it did not measure the public's reception or the international impact of his speeches.

2.3.3 Relevance and Theoretical Framework

It is safe to conclude that CDA/CDS is the most suitable methodology for this research. However, the methodological shortcomings in reviewed studies and scholarly criticism of CDA/CDS highlight the need for a multi-faceted approach. This research will therefore incorporate both linguistic and visual analyses, along with methods to assess youth reception, providing a more comprehensive understanding of war discourse.

Theoretically, Kress and van Leeuwen's concept of "multimodality," which analyses communication through multiple semiotic modes (text, images, sound) as a whole, has gained influence in fields like Social Semiotics and CDA/CDS (Catalano and Waugh 2020). Early linguistic research, as discussed in Section [2.3.1](#) and noted by O'Halloran

(2004), focused solely on language, neglecting other meaning-making resources. Kress and van Leeuwen's seminal book (2001) "Multimodal Discourse" challenges this, arguing that modern communication requires a unified semiotic approach, especially with digital advancements. Scholars like Machin and Mayr have further developed this by integrating multimodality with a critical perspective, forming MCDA. This integration of Multimodal Discourse and CDA remains rare, making it a valuable framework for analysing social media war discourse.

To assess the perception on younger demographics and its long-term effects, an ethnographic approach will be employed. Ethnography, as highlighted in previous critiques of CDA/CDS and by Hammersley and Atkinson (2007), provides a holistic understanding of how such discourses are perceived and interpreted within their cultural and social contexts.

2.3.4 Machin and Mayr's MCDA

MCDA is a research method that combines linguistic and visual tools to critically analyse discourse. In Machin and Mayr's MCDA (2023, pp. 28-32), they introduce a social semiotic perspective on language, defining MCDA as a method to reveal how communication—through both language and visuals—perpetuates social inequalities, ideologies, and power structures. This broadens the scope of communication beyond spoken or written language to include images, sounds, graphs, and other semiotic resources. They argue (*ibid*) that all forms of communication are constructed through semiotic choices available to the communicator.

Machin and Mayr (*ibid*, pp. 20) focus on various types of visual communication, including images, film clips, infographics, and social media posts, while emphasising the central role of language in these contexts. They note that linguistic information is often combined with visuals in formats like bullet lists, tables, and infographics, or in

everyday contexts such as packaging and social media (ibid). This highlights that language is frequently encountered in short text segments rather than full sentences, reflecting how multimodal elements work together to create meaning and shape social understanding. The aim of MCDA is thus to investigate these choices, exploring why particular semiotic resources are used and what ideologies or social relations they reinforce.

2.4 Conclusion

In summary, this literature review has traced the evolution of strategic communication, information warfare, and social media as a powerful “troika” shaping contemporary conflicts. Governments increasingly rely on social media for rapid, direct communication, raising concerns about misinformation, disinformation, and propaganda—especially among younger users. While previous research has examined the geopolitical backdrop of the Second Nagorno-Karabakh War and partially addressed social media and IW, a comparative analysis of leaders’ social media discourse, framed within a robust theoretical lens of MCDA and informed by youth reception, remains underexplored.

By merging Machin and Mayr’s MCDA with ethnographic insights, this study seeks to fill that gap, offering a more comprehensive view of how Prime Minister Nikol Pashinyan and President Ilham Aliyev deployed social media and why their narratives matter for post-conflict reconciliation and media literacy efforts. These findings will not only highlight the potency of StratCom and IW in modern warfare but also underscore the crucial role of critical media education in mitigating polarisation among younger demographics.

3.0 Methodology

This section outlines the methodology employed to critically analyse the social media posts by both heads of state during the Second Nagorno-Karabakh War based on a theoretical framework that combines MCDA with ethnography.

3.1 Research Design

The research employs a qualitative approach to analyse both the content of social media posts and the perspectives of youth affected by these communications. The design is twofold: first, MCDA of social media posts by the heads of government of Armenia and Azerbaijan during the war; second, ethnography with university students from both countries. This mixed-methods approach is well-suited for examining how state leaders used digital platforms during the conflict and how these messages were received, particularly by young people, who are ardent social media users. Although this project may appear ambitious for a dissertation, it addresses a critical gap in understanding how official social media narratives intersect with youth perceptions in an active conflict setting. To maintain feasibility, the study narrows its focus to Facebook as the platform of choice and a limited set of interview participants. This balance ensures depth while keeping data collection and analysis within practical constraints. Details of each is appended below:

3.1.1 Facebook Posts Selection and MCDA Analysis

A total of 303 Facebook posts were made during the war by both heads of state: 114 by Prime Minister Nikol Pashinyan and 189 by President Ilham Aliyev. This study focuses on the 10 most engaged posts (5 from each) due to the study's limited scope and a focus on depth over breadth, recommended by Machin and Mayr (2023) for comprehensive MCDA. To ensure objectivity, the posts were selected based on

engagement metrics, obtained through a publicly available Social Media Analytics toolkit, as Facebook's native tool is no longer accessible. The 10 x most engaged posts based on engagement metrics are attached as **Appendix-I** and hyperlinked to actual Facebook posts. These posts were mostly made in respective language (unless specified) and have been translated with the assistance of native speakers from the Diplomatic Academy of Vienna for Azerbaijani and the American University of Armenia for Armenian. Instances where Nikol Pashinyan's words have been dynamically transliterated are highlighted in parentheses, with the original word also provided.

MCDA was used to deconstruct the multimodal elements (text, images, videos) of these posts, revealing underlying narratives, ideologies, rhetoric, and discursive scripts using analysis tools tailored to each post, and analysing StratCom, IW/IO aspects. A brief overview of MCDA tools is provided below:

- i. **Discourse**: Machin and Mayr (2023, pp. 32) align with CDA scholars like Fairclough, van Dijk, and Wodak in viewing discourse as more than linguistic structures; they represent broader ideas communicated through texts. Discourses shape how individuals interpret social practices and relations, functioning as models of the world.
- ii. **Discursive Scripts**: Drawing on van Leeuwen (2023, pp. 29-30), Machin and Mayr describe discursive scripts as frameworks consisting of participants, actions, settings, and outcomes. These scripts frame events and participants in ways that reinforce ideologies or biases.
- iii. **Connecting Texts to Societies – Three Levels of Analysis**: Machin and Mayr align with Fairclough's framework (pp. 34-37). At the micro-level, the focus is on the material forms of communication, such as text and images, and the semiotic choices made to convey meaning. The meso-level examines how texts

are produced, distributed, and consumed, exploring how discursive practices like branding or social media discussions influence meaning-making. Finally, the macro-level looks at the broader social, cultural, and ideological contexts in which these discursive practices occur, highlighting how norms such as neoliberal ideologies shape communication.

- iv. **Analytical Tools**: Machin and Mayr (2023) outline various analytical tools in MCDA to examine the interplay between language and visuals in communication. Transitivity Analysis (pp. 81-90) focuses on the portrayal of agents in actions, addressing issues of agency and responsibility. Modality and Evaluation (pp. 91-100) scrutinise expressions of certainty and obligation to reveal biases. Visual Semiotic Analysis (pp. 101-110) looks at how visual elements combine with language to support or challenge ideologies. Intertextuality and Interdiscursivity (pp. 111-120) investigate how texts reference other discourses for context. Narrative Analysis (pp. 121-130) explores storytelling techniques used to shape public perception and legitimize actions, while Lexical Choice and Connotation (pp. 131-140) focus on word choices to uncover emotional or ideological impacts. Genre Analysis (pp. 141-150) assesses how texts follow or deviate from genre norms in political communication. Critical Pragmatics (pp. 151-160) analyses context to reveal implied meanings and socio-political implications. Multimodal Cohesion (pp. 171-180) examines how text and images combine to form a cohesive message.

Although the theoretical basis of these MCDA tools was introduced in Chapter 2, here they serve as the practical framework guiding the in-depth analysis of each Facebook post. Specifically, the researcher used this toolkit to identify linguistic and visual cues, contextual factors (e.g., time of posting, official announcements), and rhetorical

strategies (e.g., use of national symbols, emotive language). Each post was coded at the micro level (word choice, visuals), meso level (distribution channels, platform mechanics), and macro level (cultural, geopolitical context)

3.1.2 Ethnographic Data Collection and Analysis

To complement the MCDA, semi-structured interviews were conducted with youth from prominent universities in Armenia and Azerbaijan. Interpretive thematic analysis was applied to identify key themes and coded related to their perceptions of digital communications during the war. This enabled the identification and interpretation of patterns within the data, ensuring that the themes emerge organically from the participants' narratives, rather than being imposed by preconceived theories or frameworks (Braun and Clarke, 2006). This inductive approach is particularly suited to exploring the experiences and perspectives of young people in Armenia and Azerbaijan regarding the war, through semi-structured interviews allowing participants to express their views in depth. Given the sensitive nature of the conflict, focus groups were avoided to prevent participants from feeling inhibited by social pressures, a concern in post-conflict settings (Smithson, 2000).

Following Braun and Clarke's (2006) six-phase guide, the researcher engaged in: (1) Familiarisation with the transcript data; (2) Initial coding, where segments of text related to war discourse or emotional responses were highlighted; (3) Searching for themes, grouping codes into broader categories (e.g., "trust in leaders," "perceived propaganda," "impact on personal relationships"); (4) Reviewing themes, refining initial categories to ensure coherence; (5) Defining and naming themes, clarifying each theme's essence and relevance to the research questions; and (6) Producing the report, integrating thematic findings into the dissertation's Discussion chapter.

Throughout this process, reflexivity logs were maintained, noting any potential researcher bias.

Participants were selected based on specific criteria: they were current or former university students from Armenia and Azerbaijan, aged 22-30, social media users and B2 level of English proficiency. A total of 12 participants (6 from each country) took part in 40–45-minute Zoom interviews. This number was considered sufficient to reach data saturation (Guest, Bunce, and Johnson, 2006). An additional 6 interviews were planned in case the desired results were not achieved. Initial participants, who were university students, were identified through academic networks, and the snowball sampling technique was later employed to recruit additional participants from their networks. Snowball sampling, a non-probability method useful for hard-to-reach populations and remote research (Naderifar, Goli, and Ghaljaie, 2017), was particularly effective given the sensitive nature of the topic and logistical challenges of conducting the study remotely.

The interview questions were structured into sections covering social media use, recollection of war communication by their own and opposing head of state, long-term effects and is attached as **Appendix II and III**, the study does not claim a strict cause-and-effect measure. Instead, participants' self-reported **perceptions, recollections, and emotional responses** serve as proxies for how war-related posts might shape or reinforce views. To guide recollection and identify temporal resonance, three key Facebook posts were selected based on engagement and significance. The first post differed based on the participant's nationality: for Azerbaijanis, it was President Aliyev's most engaged early post, marking the start of the conflict; for Armenians, it was Prime Minister Pashinyan's post calling on the Armenian diaspora to rally. The second and third posts were the same for all participants: Aliyev's announcement of

the capture of Shusha/Shushi and Pashinyan's Facebook Live announcing the ceasefire.

3.2 Research Questions

The research questions will analyse communications by heads of state on social media during the war, and focus on how these messages shaped perceptions, and intergroup dynamics in Armenia and Azerbaijan.

- I. How did Facebook accounts of President Ilham Aliyev of Azerbaijan and Prime Minister Nikol Pashinyan of Armenia present the war discourse on Facebook, including their use of discursive scripts and rhetoric?
- II. How does the social media discourse of President Ilham Aliyev and Prime Minister Nikol Pashinyan potentially amplify—or mitigate—long-held ideologies, existing biases, and social divides?
- III. To what extent did the content shared by Facebook accounts of President Ilham Aliyev of Azerbaijan and Prime Minister Nikol Pashinyan of Armenia on social media resonate with young people on both sides, and was there any correlation with the events occurring on ground?
- IV. What are the long-term effects of the social media discourse surrounding the Second Nagorno-Karabakh War on young people from Armenia and Azerbaijan, their community relations, peacebuilding efforts, and societal cohesion in the region?
- V. In what ways do the uses of StratCom and IW on social media during the Second Nagorno-Karabakh War reflect evolving tactics in modern conflicts, and how might these developments shape the future weaponisation of social media?

3.3 Epistemological Underpinnings

This research is grounded in a constructivist paradigm, which posits that knowledge is constructed through social interactions (Bryman, 2016). This perspective is well-suited for analysing social media discourse, as it highlights how discourses both shape and are shaped by social realities (Berger and Luckmann, 1966). Constructivism asserts that meaning is created through social interactions, with individuals interpreting the world based on their experiences and cultural backgrounds (Lincoln and Guba, 1985). In this study, the constructivist approach recognises that communications by heads of state during the Second Nagorno-Karabakh War are not objective reports, but constructs designed to influence perceptions (Gergen, 1999). MCDA fits within this paradigm, as it examines both textual and multimodal elements to reveal how digital content is crafted to persuade and reinforce worldviews, especially in conflict and StratCom contexts (Fairclough, 2013). The ethnographic component, using semi-structured interviews with Armenian and Azerbaijani youth, further aligns with constructivism, exploring how individuals interpret digital communications within their cultural contexts (Hammersley and Atkinson, 2019). By focusing on youth perspectives, this study acknowledges the subjective nature of knowledge and the role of context in shaping understanding.

3.4 Ethical Considerations

Ethical considerations are paramount in this study due to the sensitive nature of the topic and potential emotional distress among participants. Ethical approval was granted by the General University Ethics Panel at the University of Stirling (GUEP 20241942214232), as outlined in **Appendix IV**, with adherence to the British Sociological Association's Ethical Guidelines for Digital Research (2017). Participants were fully informed of the study's purpose through an information sheet, and written

consent was obtained. To ensure privacy, all names and identifying information were anonymised. Participants were also given the option to decline uncomfortable questions and were provided information about free mental health services in their countries. Data was securely stored on the University OneDrive with password protection, in compliance with the UK Data Protection Act (2018).

Validity was ensured by using credible sources and a systematic approach to data selection. Facebook posts from the official accounts of Armenian Prime Minister Nikol Pashinyan and Azerbaijani President Ilham Aliyev were collected, with engagement metrics compiled using a social media analytics toolkit, ensuring objective selection based on likes, shares, and comments. Academic sources, peer-reviewed journals, books, and official government and INGO/NGO websites provided a robust foundation for analysis. Reliability was maintained through consistent data analysis processes, following established theoretical and methodological frameworks (Daymon and Holloway, 2011). The researcher, an outsider to the conflict, further mitigated potential bias, allowing for a neutral perspective (Smith, 2018).

3.5 Limitations

While this research offers valuable insights into the communications by heads of state during the Second Nagorno-Karabakh War, several limitations should be acknowledged. One limitation is that the researcher is not from Armenia or Azerbaijan, potentially lacking deep cultural and historical knowledge of the region. However, an in-depth literature review and a focused understanding of cultural and lexical nuances helped mitigate this to some extent. Another limitation is the reliance on Facebook posts, which may not fully capture the scope of digital communications or public discourse in the region. Social media algorithms influence engagement, possibly skewing the data toward more sensational content (Gillespie, 2018) and excluding less

popular but significant posts. Additionally, the exclusion of platforms like X (formerly Twitter), Instagram, Telegram and local social media may have left out other important discourses and audiences. This study analysed only ten Facebook posts—five each from President Ilham Aliyev and Prime Minister Nikol Pashinyan—based on engagement metrics. While this narrow sample may limit the breadth of analysis, it was a deliberate methodological choice to allow in-depth multimodal analysis, as recommended by Machin and Mayr (2023). MCDA is a resource-intensive method requiring granular linguistic and visual scrutiny; hence, a focused dataset ensured analytical rigour. This limitation also reflects practical constraints regarding time, translation accuracy, and scope within the dissertation's word limit. As such, the selected posts are not exhaustive of all discourse during the war but are representative of the most impactful content shared by each leader during the conflict.

The semi-structured interviews with Armenian and Azerbaijani youth also present limitations. The reliance on snowball sampling may have introduced some bias, as further participants were recruited through university cohorts, potentially reflecting a specific segment of the population and limiting the diversity of perspectives. Additionally, the selection criteria, such as English proficiency and university preference, may not fully represent the broader youth population, excluding those outside the academic environment or non-English speakers. These factors could further restrict the generalisability of the findings. Moreover, the sensitive nature of the conflict may have influenced participants' openness, leading to socially desirable responses or withheld views due to fear of reprisal or emotional distress, despite efforts to mitigate this. Finally, the study is limited to the war's timeframe, restricting its ability to examine the long-term entrenched biases and ideologies and their effect on the discourse and youth in both the countries.

4.0 Findings

The individual analysis of each Facebook post is attached as Appendix-VI and has been coded for ease of citation and hyperlinked within this chapter, e.g., posts by President Ilham Aliyev (IA-1 to IA-5) and posts by Prime Minister Nikol Pashinyan (NP-1 to NP-5). NVivo software was used to assist with the thematic analysis of the interviews, and a screenshot of both themes, codes and coded transcript is attached as Appendix V. The sample included 12 participants, six from Azerbaijan (coded AZ-P1 to AZ-P6) and six from Armenia (coded AR-P1 to AR-P6), with an equal number of men and women from diverse backgrounds, from current students to recent graduates and working professionals, aged between 22-26 years. The Interpretive thematic analysis identified five key themes that emerged from the interviews: social media habits, trust in communication, war discourse and rhetoric perception, responses to key war events, and the long-term effects on peacebuilding and societal cohesion. Each research question is discussed with support from these themes and participants' quotes, offering in-depth context to the MCDA analysis and insights into the social media experiences of young people during the war. As shown in the **Appendix V** screenshot, codes were grouped into broader themes following Braun and Clarke's (2006) six-phase approach (familiarisation, coding, searching for themes, reviewing, defining/naming, and writing). By integrating NVivo queries (e.g., word frequency searches, coded segment comparisons), the study ensured a systematic thematic analysis, aligning with the interpretive paradigm outlined in Chapter 3.

4.1 RQ-1

Facebook was used by both leaders as a StratCom platform (each with their distinct approach) to present their narrative on the war, and it allowed both the leaders to bypass traditional gatekeepers and address their publics directly with all participants

reporting consumption of content. This finding resonates with the argument by (Howard and Kollanyi, 2016) that digital platforms reduce traditional media's gatekeeping role.

- i. **President Ilham Aliyev**. All analysed posts, except one, feature the slogan "Karabakh is Azerbaijan!" ([IA-1](#), [IA-2](#), [IA-3](#), [IA-5](#)), its repetition across posts strengthened national identity, unified the population, and framed the war as a justified reclamation of Azerbaijan's rightful land. This slogan became a rallying cry, reinforcing Azerbaijan's non-negotiable claim to Nagorno-Karabakh and lending legal and historical legitimacy to the military actions ([IA-1](#), [IA-3](#)). Aliyev's focus on this phrase simplified the complex ethnic and self-determination disputes, making the issue more accessible to the Azerbaijani public. It united the public around territorial integrity and national pride ([IA-2](#), [IA-5](#)). The slogan became the centrepiece of Azerbaijani StratCom effort during the war ([IA-3](#)), justifying military actions and positioning Azerbaijan as the rightful victor domestically and internationally. Its use is comparable to other territorial slogans like "Crimea is Ours" by Russia (Associated Press, 2024) and "One China" by China (Chinese Foreign Ministry, 2010), illustrating how slogans can be weaponised for political objectives and support consolidation. Such nationalistic slogans also align with van Dijk's (2006) ideological square, which highlights how in-group positivity and out-group negativity can be amplified by repetitive discourse. By asserting "Karabakh is Azerbaijan," Aliyev foregrounds a positive self-representation (Azerbaijan's justified claim) and implicitly negates any competing Armenian claim (negative other representation). Aliyev's posts notably omitted references to casualties or the humanitarian cost, focusing instead on victories and territorial gains to maintain public and military morale ([IA-2](#)). In addition to rhetoric, Aliyev's

posts employed visuals to reinforce military strength and national pride. Images of military themes and national symbols (raised fists, flags, blurred military assets) were strategically placed to evoke pride and resilience ([IA-1](#), [IA-5](#)). The use of these symbols, combined with assertive slogans, created a cohesive visual and rhetorical narrative emphasising the inevitability of Azerbaijani victory.

- ii. **Reception by Youth in Azerbaijan**. All interviewed Azerbaijani participants followed the President's social media platforms directly for war updates, rarely relying on intermediary platforms. They expressed a strong sense of national pride, particularly in response to posts celebrating military victories, such as the capture of Shusha ([IA-5](#)). Aliyev's posts, for them, provided legitimacy, reinforcing the belief that the conflict was about rightfully reclaiming lost territory. None of the participants raised concerns about the discursive elements in his posts. This sentiment is encapsulated in a quote from AZ-P1 (Male, 22) regarding [IA-5](#). *"There's a famous quote from that speech, Dear Shusha, you are finally free. It's still in the hearts and minds of many Azerbaijanis"*, it underscores the emotional resonance that slogans can have in conflict communication.
- iii. **Prime Minister Nikol Pashinyan**. Prime Minister Pashinyan's posts presented an emotionally driven narrative, focusing on national unity, sacrifice, and justifying Armenia's military defeat. This resonates with Wodak's (2015) insights that populist narratives often emphasise historical grievances and martyrdom. Unlike Aliyev, Pashinyan largely avoided engaging with specific wartime events, except for one post ([NP-1](#)) after the ceasefire which was to quell protests against his government. His rhetoric centred on martyrdom and communal suffering, portraying Armenia as a nation under siege but morally intact. By attributing the defeat to past corruption and systemic mismanagement, Pashinyan positioned

himself as a leader making the best of a dire situation, emphasising the idea of sacrifice—by both soldiers and civilians—and casting himself as a servant of the nation ([NP-1](#), [NP-5](#)). In posts like [NP-2](#), [NP-3](#), and [NP-4](#), Pashinyan connected the Nagorno-Karabakh conflict to a broader historical narrative of Armenian resilience and survival, framing the war as part of a centuries-long struggle for the right to exist. This rhetoric was intended to mobilise not only the military but the entire Armenian nation, including the diaspora, calling for international recognition of Nagorno-Karabakh's self-determination. Prime Minister Pashinyan's use of visuals further reinforced this emotionally charged narrative featuring solemn imagery, such as addressing soldiers at night and mourning fallen soldiers ([NP-2](#), [NP-5](#)), visually emphasising the themes of sacrifice, national unity, and resilience. He also used visuals of global protests ([NP-4](#)) by the Armenian diaspora, to extend this narrative beyond Armenia's borders, appealing for global support.

- iv. **Reception by Youth in Armenia**. The reception of these posts by Armenian youth contrasted with the likely intended objectives. Half of the interviewed participants followed Colonel Artsrun Hovhannisyan—in addition to or instead of the Prime Minister—for war updates. Additionally, the setbacks on the ground compelled participants to seek information from Telegram and other sources. Both these factors prevented the Prime Minister's Facebook page—which had more followers than Aliyev's and better international recognition than a MoD press secretary—from fully realising its potential to mitigate the growing search for truth amid the fog of war. They also recalled the prominent slogan "#WeWillWin" (in contrast to "Karabakh is Azerbaijan") during the war, which was notably absent from any of the Prime Minister's most engaged posts analysed. His posts ([NP-2](#), [NP-3](#), [NP-5](#)) were instead focused on evoking deep emotions, particularly when discussing the

loss of soldiers and the significance of defending the homeland. Despite feeling devastated by the ceasefire agreement revealed in [NP-1](#), some participants noted that, “it wasn’t entirely his fault” —a sentiment that they attributed to the empathy his speeches generated. However, all participants expressed a complete loss of trust and deception in his communication after that post—a sentiment that precipitated to other government accounts they followed. AR-P6 (Male,22) even went as far as to say, *“He could have said something sooner, and maybe this whole war wouldn’t have happened. I can’t say for sure, but it’s very sad and disappointing. The president said everything would be fine, but it wasn’t, and they’re still in office with no replacements. I’m sorry, I can’t say exactly how we could have prevented this. But if he had signed the agreement the same day the war started, people might have reacted the same way, but at least we might not have lost so many lives”*. Such an erosion of trust aligns with Relationship Management Theory (Ledingham 2003), where perceived discrepancies between official narratives and on-ground realities can dissolve the relational bonds, leaders have with their audiences.

4.2 RQ-2

The omission of humanitarian concerns, selective portrayal of conflict realities, and emphasis on national pride and historical narratives in both leaders’ posts reinforced existing power structures, biases, and divisive ideologies. These findings support Moloney’s (2006) critique that communication strategies often reinforce dominant power structures by normalising one-sided perspectives. Similarly, Snow (2010) posits that selective reality construction is central to propaganda efforts, a tactic both leaders employed here. Each leader strengthened their nation’s claims while delegitimising the opposition, leaving little room for dialogue or reconciliation. This aligns with

Wodak's (2015) analysis of right-wing populist discourse, which often employs nationalism and historical revisionism to marginalise opponents. Both President Aliyev and Prime Minister Pashinyan used national pride and historical claims to foster internal unity while undermining dialogue and peace efforts. Drawing from Propaganda in the Post-Truth Era (Kucharski, 2019), selective reality construction is a key tool in modern political communication. Both leaders highlighted conflict aspects that aligned with their strategic goals, omitting humanitarian concerns. This approach, evident in their social media posts, perpetuated narratives favouring nationalism over dialogue, deepening the divide between the two nations and making peace more elusive during and after the war.

- i. **President Ilham Aliyev**. A key element in Aliyev's discourse was the symbolic representation of long-held ideologies and biases, exemplified by the Khudafarin bridges ([IA-2](#)). These bridges, with significant cultural and historical value (UNESCO n.d.), symbolised not only the reclamation of territorial sovereignty but also cultural heritage. By showcasing the captured Khudafarin bridges ([IA-2](#)) as a backdrop, Aliyev projected a narrative of historical reclamation and national restoration. This symbolism contributed to an exclusionary narrative of Azerbaijani identity, delegitimising Armenia and its claims. By foregrounding Khudafarin bridges and ignoring civilian cost, Aliyev effectively enacts van Dijk's (1998) "ideological polarisation", in which positive representation of the in-group ("our cultural heritage reclaimed") is pitted against the negative or invisible representation of the out-group's suffering. Aliyev's discourse framed the war as a non-negotiable effort to restore historical rights, excluding any possibility of peace or dialogue. His posts frequently used representational strategies that highlighted symbols of victory, while abstracting or omitting the humanitarian impact, which

increased divisiveness and was met with disdain by Armenian youth. For example, Khudafarin bridges ([IA-2](#)) and city of Shusha ([IA-5](#)) were foregrounded, while the realities of the conflict—such as displacement, destruction, and civilian casualties—were strategically ignored. This selective abstraction allowed Aliyev to present a version of the conflict, one where Azerbaijan was reclaiming what was lost, and Armenian views including any suffering or loss was either downplayed or ignored. AR-P6 (Male, 22) expressed this, *“Yes, I’m Armenian, so seeing someone claim our lands and cities would naturally make me mad. Sometimes I would see similar posts from Aliyev on Instagram. I didn’t follow him, but I would still see the posts and they made me angry”*.

- ii. **Prime Minister Nikol Pashinyan**. Pashinyan’s discourse also largely excluded the opposing side’s perspective, presenting a one-sided narrative that reinforced nationalistic ideologies ([NP-2](#), [NP-4](#)). His posts did not engage with the Azerbaijani narrative of territorial reclamation, instead focusing solely on Armenia’s right to defend its homeland and right to self-determination for the ethnic Armenians of Nagorno-Karabakh. This mirrors Wodak’s (2015) analysis of nationalistic discourse that can marginalise dialogue by portraying the out-group solely as aggressors and the in-group as righteous victims or defenders. This narrative resonated deeply with the Armenian public which was a common theme in the interviews with Armenian participants but also contributed towards the broader divisiveness between the two countries, as it left no room for dialogue or reconciliation.

4.3 RQ-3

According to interviews with young people from Azerbaijan and Armenia, both Aliyev’s and Pashinyan’s social media content resonated deeply with their respective and

opposing publics. There was a strong correlation between events on the ground and the social media content shared by both leaders, with posts from Aliyev and Pashinyan either reflecting key military developments or shaping public perception in real time due to the situation on the ground. Azerbaijani participants noted that President Aliyev's posts, particularly the slogan "Karabakh is Azerbaijan," were instrumental in creating a sense of national unity. Posts celebrating military victories, such as the capture of Shusha ([IA-5](#)), evoked feelings of pride and joy. All participants reported waiting for this announcement before celebrating, despite the post lacking documentary evidence of the capture and denials from the Armenian MoD press secretaries. This quote from AZ-P5 (Female, 23) encapsulates this moment, *"No, I didn't wait for any video confirmation. As soon as I saw the post, we were already celebrating. I remember I was in the car, and we were celebrating on the roads. We were dancing in the parks, and everyone was celebrating and hugging each other, waving flags"*. Armenian youth did not appreciate the content shared by Aliyev; however, some followed his posts to monitor "what the other side was doing" or reported incidental news consumption especially on Instagram.

Armenian participants, on the other hand, expressed feelings of grief and anger as the war progressed, particularly in response to Pashinyan's post announcing the ceasefire ([NP-1](#)). While his oratory skills in posts about sacrifice and martyrdom ([NP-2](#) and [NP-5](#)) showed resonance with the Armenian youth interviewed, there was also frustration. The dissonance between the content of his posts and the reality on the ground—such as the fall of Shusha—led to a sense of betrayal among many Armenian participants. Consequently, all Armenian participants ultimately reported a complete loss of trust in his communication. 2 Azerbaijani participants also reported following

Nikol Pashinyan Facebook page during the war however, they all encountered the ceasefire announcement from social media sources.

A significant theme across both Armenian and Azerbaijani participants was the fluctuating trust in their respective governments' communications before, during and after the 44-day war. None of the participants believed their leader conveyed the objective truth during the war. They acknowledged that certain information was withheld, accessible only through unfiltered platforms such as Telegram or the personal accounts of soldiers on the battlefield. Azerbaijani participants started the war with lesser trust level in President Ilham Aliyev communication but maintained a relatively higher level of trust during and towards the end of the war. Armenian participants experienced a complete reversal in trust levels. While their initial trust in the Prime Minister's communication was high, particularly at the onset of the war, none of the participants trusted his messages by the war's end.

4.4 RQ-4

The social media discourse during the war has left lasting impressions on the younger generations on both sides, which is deeply concerning and has made reconciliation difficult. Young people have developed deep rooted feelings of hate in this vacuum and existing echo chambers. This is in line with existing literature, such as Pariser (2011), which states that social media algorithms often promote user specific content by showing users content that aligns with their preferences, contributing to polarisation. Research on echo chambers by Sunstein (2007) shows how they can entrench views and lead to heightened emotions, including hate. Likewise in the interviews, participants reported that hate speech and misinformation on social media exacerbated tensions and made it harder to envision peace in the future. A significant but disturbing aspect was that each side believed that the other side is taught hatred

against them. Armenian participants reported that Azerbaijani youth are taught Anti-Armenian sentiments since an early age, AR-P4 said, *“their school curriculum is full of hate towards Armenians—they always teach that Armenians conquered their territories, and being Armenian is used as an insult. Ilham Aliyev even said he’s happy that today’s generation in Azerbaijan hates Armenians”*. Azerbaijani participants also reported similar but opposing sentiment against Armenians, AZ-P3 said, *“On the ground, there’s undeniable hatred from both sides. For example, Armenian children are taught to hate the Turks, and that refers not only to Turkey but to all Turkic nations in general”*. Upon being asked if they would make any friends from the other side both Armenians and Azerbaijanis were found reluctant and blamed both the war and its social media discourse as one of the reasons for this.

A few participants acknowledged attempts by diasporan communities or liberal-minded individuals to promote peace through online platforms, but these efforts were described as marginal and often met with hostility. The idea of peacebuilding through social media was seen as unrealistic by most, who believed that in-person interaction would be more effective. Overall, the long-term effects of the war discourse on social media have left participants feeling cynical about the future of relations between Armenia and Azerbaijan. Many participants described their generation as having grown up without direct contact with the other side, making it difficult to envision reconciliation or peace without significant effort from both societies and international intervention.

Another concerning theme across the interviews was incidental news consumption and the non-reliance on legacy media, which aligns with existing literature on young people increasingly relying on social media for news (see section [2.1.2](#)). Participants from both Azerbaijan and Armenia highlighted how they frequently encountered war-

related news on platforms primarily used for personal or social interactions, particularly Instagram. In both countries, young people noted how social media blurred the lines between entertainment and war-related content. This incidental news consumption led to emotional saturation, with participants feeling overwhelmed by the volume of war-related content, and Armenian youth reporting significant mental discomfort.

4.5 RQ-5

The analysis of both President Aliyev's and Prime Minister Pashinyan's social media posts clearly demonstrates how social media is evolving as a powerful tool in modern warfare. Both leaders utilised StratCom and IO/IW to control narratives, bolster public morale, and counter the opposition's messaging. This suggests an evolving trend where social media platforms are increasingly weaponised in modern warfare, playing a key role in psychological operations, propaganda, and national mobilisation. As Nilsson and Ekman (2024) highlight in the Russia-Ukraine conflict, the mediatization of war has been notably evident, while Mualla (2017) points to the Israeli Palestinian cyber conflict as a clear example of how Facebook is used for propaganda and StratCom purposes by IDF.

- i. **President Ilham Aliyev**. President Aliyev's posts typified the application of StratCom, where communication was mission-oriented and designed to support Azerbaijan's policy objectives (Paul, 2011; [Section 2.1.1](#)). His use of social media demonstrated a clear understanding of how to synchronise actions, messages, and images to advance national interests, a sign of contemporary StratCom. Aliyev's omission of casualties in posts like [IA-1](#) helped control the war narrative and prevent demoralisation among Azerbaijani citizens, a tactic rooted in IW principles. By emphasising territorial claims and national strength, he maintained control over domestic discourse and countered Armenian narratives that could

have weakened public confidence. His posts targeted both domestic and Armenian audiences, with visual evidence of territorial control shaping perceptions on the battlefield and internationally. His use of a singular political slogan exemplifies effective StratCom, condensing complex objectives into a simple, widely adoptable message. Aliyev's announcement of the capture of Shusha highlights his strategic use of timing and simplicity in an IW/IO context. The post focused solely on Shusha's liberation, ensuring clarity and authority. This aligns with IW tactics, where simplicity and precision are key to psychological operations aimed at demoralising the enemy and reinforcing a sense of victory. The capture of Shusha was a turning point, and Aliyev's control over the timing and content of this announcement further demonstrated his use of these tactics.

- ii. **Prime Minister Nikol Pashinyan**. Nikol Pashinyan's use of StratCom and IW reflects both the potential and the peril of social media in modern warfare. His communication, while emotionally charged and aimed at rallying national unity, was decentralised, reactive and increasingly detached from the military realities on the ground. Despite initial attempts to align the war effort with long-standing political objectives, such as self-determination for Nagorno-Karabakh, Pashinyan's messaging failed to effectively manage the psychological impact of significant territorial losses and the fallout from eventual ceasefire. He successfully invoked themes of sacrifice and historical struggle, framing the conflict as a continuation of Armenia's centuries-long fight for survival ([NP-2](#), [NP-3](#), [NP-4](#), [NP-5](#)). This served as an element of IW, aiming to rally the population and maintain a united front against Azerbaijan. By focusing on the martyrdom of Armenian soldiers, Pashinyan also attempted to maintain public morale, even as the situation on the ground deteriorated. However, Pashinyan's reliance on emotional

rhetoric became a double-edged sword. Whilst it helped sustain morale in the initial stages of the conflict, it also created unrealistic expectations about the war's potential outcome. The lack of transparent and coordinated communication about military defeats and the possibility of a ceasefire led to a growing sense of frustration among Armenians, particularly the younger generation. His failure to pivot toward a more clear, unified and transparent communication strategy as the war progressed, particularly around the issue of a ceasefire, contributed to the growing sense of frustration and disillusionment among the Armenian public. For instance, whilst Stepanyan and Hovhannisyian were both responsible for official updates (as discussed in section [2.2.4](#)), their posts often diverged from the narrative Pashinyan was trying to maintain. This fragmentation was evident in the way different aspects of the war were emphasised—military victories by Hovhannisyian, humanitarian crises by Stepanyan, and national sacrifice by Pashinyan. This inconsistent messaging contributed to the confusion and sense of betrayal felt by the Armenian public. On 9th November whilst Stepanyan and Hovhannisyian were posting on Armenian military resilience, Pashinyan's Facebook Live announcement about the ceasefire next morning highlighted the gravity of the territorial losses, creating a stark contrast in the public narrative (see their posts from 9th November below). Thus, it can be argued that social media can be a powerful tool for shaping public perception and maintaining morale, but it can also exacerbate public discontent if not aligned with ground realities. Pashinyan's messaging shows that emotional appeals alone are not enough to sustain public support in the face of military defeat. His ultimate reliance on emotional narratives, without addressing the shifting political and military objectives, left the Armenian population unprepared for the ceasefire and the

significant territorial losses that followed. Social media can amplify StratCom and IW, but in modern warfare, it must be balanced with tangible success on the ground. It cannot serve as a substitute for military victory, nor can it be crafted in isolation from broader political objectives.

Fig 3 and 4, Facebook Posts of Stepanyan and Hovhannisyan denying Shusha Capture - 9

4.5 Practical Implications and Application

The use of Facebook by both leaders shows the growing importance of social media platforms as a direct communication tool for political leaders in addition to legacy media. While broadcast press conferences typically follow a structured timetable and may be subject to editorial oversight, social media posts offer immediate, unfiltered channels through which leaders can connect with citizens. For instance, participants such as AZ-P3 described refreshing President Aliyev’s Facebook page in real time for battlefield updates—an experience distinct from waiting for an evening news segment. Additionally, algorithms on platforms like Facebook can intensify the visibility of specific posts (Pariser, 2011), further distinguishing social media’s role in shaping public discourse from traditional broadcast methods. As highlighted by the interviews, younger generations are increasingly turning to non-traditional news sources, and this trend holds true even in countries with state-owned media. As a result, maintaining an official presence on these platforms becomes even more critical for ensuring that the

government's message reaches its target audience. Beyond the message itself, participants frequently noted the medium's influence on their experiences. For instance, AR-P2 cited social media's 'instant updates and direct uploads' as more appealing than state TV, which felt 'slow and censored.' This preference underscores how the *medium* plays a pivotal role in shaping audience engagement and trust. For Aliyev, social media became a powerful vehicle for promoting national unity and downplaying negative aspects like casualties. This allowed for real-time updates that could influence public perception, bypassing journalistic critique or alternative narratives. Thus, the implication is clear: social media offers a powerful platform to engage with the public, build consensus, and control wartime narratives. However, it also requires alignment with ground realities, as evidenced by the decline in public trust in Pashinyan's messaging when his posts failed to reflect the true scope of military losses. This erosion of trust is in line with existing PR theories, such as Situational Crisis Communication Theory (Coombs, 2007), which emphasises the importance of truthful communication during crises, and Relationship Management Theory (Ledingham, 2003), where deceitful messaging leads to a breakdown in the trust essential for maintaining healthy public relationships.

The findings show that social media can be weaponised to amplify nationalistic rhetoric and entrench unequal power structures. This tactic is likely to be used in future conflicts, where historical grievances and territorial disputes can be easily distilled into slogans and images that rally public sentiment. However, this also risks increasing polarisation and exacerbating long-standing ethnic or political divides, making reconciliation more difficult post-conflict. For peacebuilders, the practical application is that any reconciliation efforts in the aftermath of future social media-driven conflict will need to account for the deep entrenchment of these narratives. The rapid

dissemination and repetition of such messages on platforms that favour polarising content complicate efforts to promote dialogue and peace and require across the board stringent content moderation regulations by social media platforms. Peacebuilding efforts in the digital age must address the long-term impact of echo chambers and algorithmic polarisation. Interventions must not only occur at the policy level but also at the algorithmic design level, encouraging platforms to promote more balanced, dialogue-driven content rather than reinforcing divisive narratives.

The over-reliance on social media for news by younger generations especially during conflicts, as observed in the Second Nagorno-Karabakh War, signals a crucial implication for future crises. As social media platforms increasingly blur the line between personal and political content, incidental news consumption is likely to overwhelm users with emotionally charged and distressing information. This will lead to increasingly mental health and wellbeing issues for younger generations and heightened vulnerability to misinformation and polarisation, as algorithms reinforce echo chambers, deepening existing biases and nationalistic sentiments. In future conflicts, the role of social media will grow, necessitating proactive strategies to counter these effects, such as enhanced media literacy programs to help users critically assess the content they consume and mental health support systems to mitigate the emotional toll of constant exposure to conflict-related content. Moreover, the erosion of trust in traditional media suggests that future communication strategies will need to integrate reliable information and fact checking into social media ecosystems to prevent disinformation from dominating the public discourse.

5.0 Conclusion

Through MCDA of selected Facebook posts by President Aliyev and Prime Minister Pashinyan, alongside ethnographic insights from young people in both countries, this research critically examined social media use during the Second Nagorno-Karabakh War. MCDA enabled a nuanced understanding of how visual and textual elements combined to convey complex messages. Ethnographic insights further enriched the analysis by revealing how these messages were received by youth, demonstrating the real-world impact of digital communication. By maintaining an impartial stance throughout the analysis, this study provided a balanced examination that avoided bias, ensuring the reliability of its conclusions. In doing so, the dissertation reinforced the “troika” idea (StratCom, IW, social media) outlined in Chapter 2, highlighting how leaders can bypass traditional media gatekeepers and exploit algorithmic channels for immediate, large-scale influence.

The findings indicate that both leaders utilised social media to construct narratives that served their political and military objectives, but with significant differences in approach, style, and impact on their respective publics. President Aliyev's social media strategy revolved around the repetitive use of the slogan "Karabakh is Azerbaijan!" This was not only an assertion of territorial integrity but a rallying cry that unified Azerbaijani citizens under a singular, easily digestible national narrative. Aliyev's focus on military victories and the reclamation of historical sovereignty omitted any mention of the humanitarian costs of war, thereby maintaining morale and public support. Conversely, Pashinyan's emotionally charged communications sought to invoke themes of sacrifice, martyrdom, and historical resilience. However, as military losses mounted, his failure to adapt his messaging to reflect these realities resulted in a significant loss of public trust among Armenian youth, as revealed by ethnographic

findings. This divergence highlights how communication can profoundly affect national morale and public perception during conflict. These outcomes also speak to Situational Crisis Communication Theory (Coombs, 2007) and Relationship Management Theory (Ledingham, 2003), which, although not discussed in the Literature Review, emerged as a key component of findings in Chapter 4, and as a useful lens for interpreting how leaders maintain—or lose—public trust under crisis conditions. While this dissertation examined Aliyev’s and Pashinyan’s posts from an “outside-in” standpoint, government and military communication teams often have sophisticated internal analytics (e.g., real-time engagement dashboards, sentiment analysis) to refine and pivot their strategies as events unfold. Collaboration with such teams could offer deeper insights into decision-making processes, yet this access is typically restricted due to security and political sensitivities. Recognising this limitation underscores the need for future studies to involve, where possible, coordinated research efforts that bridge external academic analysis with insider data.

Recent work by We Are Social (2024) also suggests that youth reliance on mobile-first, visually oriented platforms has grown across the globe including conflict zones, further heightening the need for critical media literacy and emotional support. Future research could build on this by exploring cross-platform behaviour (e.g., Instagram, TikTok, YouTube) and how evolving features—like short-form videos or ephemeral content—intensify these dynamics. Moreover, the study reiterates that social media (the third element in the troika) can either amplify violence-supportive narratives or foster online dialogues aimed at peace—depending on how political leaders, platform policies, and grassroots initiatives intersect. The ultimate challenge lies in balancing nationalistic or strategic objectives with ethical communication, ensuring that StratCom and IW do not irreparably harm prospects for future reconciliation.

In conclusion, this research enhances the understanding of evolving StratCom and IW in the digital age, wherein social media stands as a pivotal battleground. It underscores that whilst leaders can harness platforms to rally public support and assert legitimacy, they risk alienating or disillusioning key demographics—particularly youth—if messages fail to reflect on-ground realities. By integrating MCDA and ethnographic methods, the study captures both the production (leaders' posts) and the reception (youth interpretations) of conflict discourse, illustrating the power of digital narratives to shape perceptions and, ultimately, the trajectory of war.

Looking ahead, future research could delve into cross-platform analyses, integrate insider analytics from government communication teams, or adopt a longitudinal lens to investigate how wartime social media narratives influence post-conflict reconciliation. As digital warfare evolves, scholars and practitioners must grapple with the ethical and strategic implications of weaponizing social media, recognising that even well-intended communication strategies can yield lasting social, political, and psychological consequences.

Appendix I - Engagement Metrics

Engagement Metrics of Top 5 x Posts of Prime Minister Nikol Pashinyan	Link/Code	Type
	1 NP-1	Facebook Live
	2 NP-2	Video with Caption
	3 NP-3	Images With Caption
	4 NP-4	Images With Caption
	5 NP-5	Image With Caption
Engagement Metrics of Top 5 x Posts of Azerbaijani President Ilham Aliyev	Link/Code	Type
	1 IA-1	Image
	2 IA-2	Video with Caption
	3 IA-3	Image
	4 IA-4	Image
	5 IA-5	Image

Appendix II Interview Questionnaire Armenia

Semi Structured Interview for Armenian Youth

Introduction

- Brief introduction of the interviewer and purpose of the interview.
- Assurance of confidentiality and voluntary participation.
- Explanation of the interview's structure.

Section 1: Background Information

1. Can you tell me a bit about yourself (age, education, occupation)?
2. Do you consider yourself to be politically aware?
3. How would you describe yourself feelings towards your country (as patriotic, or apolitical or not interested) (Follow up- give your own definition if you are)?
4. How often do you use social media and which platforms do you use the most and how?
5. How much time do you spend on social media? Any online debates/ conversations/ influencers that you follow etc?
6. Which media do you prefer for news and is it same for your peers and why? (Legacy or digital media)
7. How do you get your news? (Follow up is news incidental or planned if on social media)
8. Do you follow any govt officials/ channels on social media?

Section 2: Experience During the War

9. Did your trust level on the Armenian Govt communication change before, during and after this war?
10. During the Second Nagorno-Karabakh War, how frequently did you follow updates on Facebook of the Government?
11. Can you recall any specific posts or types of content that stood out to you during the war?

Section 3: Impact of Digital Communication

12. Were there any messages or images that had a strong impact on you? (Show key Facebook posts from Armenian PM and Azerbaijan President)
 - Post 1: [Armenian Diaspora Post by Armenian PM]
<https://www.facebook.com/100044139324388/posts/2776185596035151/>
 - Post 2: [Shusha Capture Post by Azerbaijan President]
<https://www.facebook.com/PresidentIlhamAliyev/photos/a.10151996474470315/10164122626875315/?type=3>
 - Post 3: [Surrender by Armenia announced by Armenian PM]
<https://www.facebook.com/431759004972073/videos/647316032616802>
13. Any posts that changed, reinforced or altered your opinion, perspective, understanding or belief during the war?
14. Do you think your government was proactive or reactive during the war on social media?

Section 4: Influence on Youth Perspectives

15. How do you think social media communication during the conflict shaped the views of your peers?
16. Did you engage in any discussions or share any content related to the war on social media? If so, what was the nature of these interactions?

Section 5: Peace and Divisiveness

17. In your opinion, is social media used to promote peace or it increases divisiveness among younger demographics?
18. Do you follow any peacebuilding or reconciliation-focused accounts or groups on social media? How effective do you find their content?

Section 6: Long-Term Effects and Reconciliation

19. What long-term effects do you think the social media discourse during the war has had on community relations and societal cohesion?
20. How do you see the role of social media in post-conflict societies like Armenia?

Conclusion

- Thank the participant for their time and insights.
- Provide information on how the findings will be used.

Ask if they have any questions or additional comments.

Appendix III Interview Questionnaire Azerbaijan

Semi Structured Interview for Azerbaijani Youth

Introduction

- Brief introduction of the interviewer and purpose of the interview.
- Assurance of confidentiality and voluntary participation.
- Explanation of the interview's structure.

Section 1: Background Information

1. Can you tell me a bit about yourself (age, education, occupation)?
2. Do you consider yourself to be politically aware?
3. How would you describe yourself feelings towards your country (as patriotic, or apolitical or not interested) (Follow up- give your own definition if you are)?
4. How often do you use social media and which platforms do you use the most and how?
5. How much time do you spend on social media? Any online debates/ conversations/ influencers that you follow etc?
6. Which media do you prefer for news and is it same for your peers and why? (Legacy or digital media)
7. How do you get your news? (Follow up is news incidental or planned if on social media)
8. Do you follow any govt officials/ channels on social media?

Section 2: Experience During the War

9. Did your trust level on the Azerbaijani Govt communication change before, during and after this war?
10. During the Second Nagorno-Karabakh War, how frequently did you follow updates on Facebook of the Government?
11. Can you recall any specific posts or types of content that stood out to you during the war?

Section 3: Impact of Digital Communication

12. Were there any messages or images that had a strong impact on you? (Show key Facebook posts from Armenian PM and Azerbaijan President)
 - Post 1: [Post of Azerbaijani President on the start of war]
<https://www.facebook.com/PresidentIlhamAliyev/photos/a.10151996474470315/10163945160230315/>
 - Post 2: [Shusha Capture Post by Azerbaijan President]
<https://www.facebook.com/PresidentIlhamAliyev/photos/a.10151996474470315/10164122626875315/?type=3>
 - Post 3: [Surrender by Armenia announced by Armenian PM]
<https://www.facebook.com/431759004972073/videos/647316032616802>
13. Any posts that changed, reinforced or altered your opinion, perspective, understanding or belief during the war?
14. Do you think your government was proactive or reactive during the war on social media?

Section 4: Influence on Youth Perspectives

15. How do you think social media communication during the conflict shaped the views of your peers?
16. Did you engage in any discussions or share any content related to the war on social media? If so, what was the nature of these interactions?

Section 5: Peace and Divisiveness

17. In your opinion, is social media used to promote peace or it increases divisiveness among younger demographics?
18. Do you follow any peacebuilding or reconciliation-focused accounts or groups on social media? How effective do you find their content?

Section 6: Long-Term Effects and Reconciliation

19. What long-term effects do you think the social media discourse during the war has had on community relations and societal cohesion?
20. How do you see the role of social media in post-conflict societies like Azerbaijan?

Conclusion

- Thank the participant for their time and insights.
- Provide information on how the findings will be used.
- Ask if they have any questions or additional comments.

Appendix IV Ethics Approval

Ethics Notification: GUEP 2024 19422 14232 Arsalan Satti David Rolinson

donotreply@infonetica.net
To: Arsalan Satti
Cc: Ethics; David Rolinson

☀️ 😊 ↩ Reply ↩ Reply all ↪ Forward 🗨️ 📧 ⋮

Tue 02/07/2024 12:19

Dear Arsalan Satti

Ethics Application Form : [The Second Nagorno-Karabakh War: A Critical Discourse Analysis of Government Communications and Impact on Youth Perspectives](#)

Ethics Reference Number : [GUEP_2024_19422_14232](#)

Thank you for your submission of the above **ethics** application.

The ethical approaches of this project have been approved and you can now proceed with your project in accordance with any comments made by the reviewers. You must check your application form for these and adhere to any recommendations the reviewers provide.

A small number of student projects that have been approved within the Faculty will be reviewed further to ensure consistency of review. You may be contacted to request amendments to your application.

Should your proposal change any amendments must be approved by your supervisor.

If you have any further queries, please do not hesitate to contact us by email to ethics@stir.ac.uk

Kind regards,

Research Integrity and Governance Team

Appendix V NVivo

Themes and Codes

The screenshot displays the NVivo software interface with a list of codes and their associated data. The interface includes a sidebar with navigation options like 'Quick Access', 'IMPORT', 'Data', 'ORGANIZE', 'Coding', 'Cases', 'Notes', 'Sets', 'EXPLORE', 'Queries', 'Visualizations', and 'Reports'. The main window shows a table of codes with columns for Name, Files, References, Created on, Created by, Modified on, and Modified by. The table is organized into a tree structure with expandable nodes.

Name	Files	References	Created on	Created by	Modified on	Modified by
Long-term Effects on Peacebuilding and Societal Cohesion	12	58	17/09/2024 13:49	AAS	17/09/2024 15:49	AAS
Decreased Friendliness	8	10	17/09/2024 16:27	AAS	17/09/2024 16:34	AAS
Engagement Online	3	4	17/09/2024 16:24	AAS	17/09/2024 16:31	AAS
Increased Friendliness	0	0	17/09/2024 16:24	AAS	17/09/2024 16:24	AAS
Negative	8	22	17/09/2024 16:18	AAS	17/09/2024 16:33	AAS
Neutral	6	8	17/09/2024 16:25	AAS	17/09/2024 16:34	AAS
Positive	2	3	17/09/2024 16:18	AAS	17/09/2024 16:28	AAS
Responses to Key War Events	12	61	17/09/2024 13:48	AAS	17/09/2024 15:48	AAS
No recollection	1	1	17/09/2024 16:41	AAS	17/09/2024 16:41	AAS
Reception From Other Media	6	7	17/09/2024 16:40	AAS	17/09/2024 16:44	AAS
Timely Reception To Aliyev	5	14	17/09/2024 16:23	AAS	17/09/2024 16:53	AAS
Timely Reception to Pashniyan	5	7	17/09/2024 16:23	AAS	17/09/2024 16:43	AAS
Social Media Habits	12	100	17/09/2024 13:48	AAS	17/09/2024 15:46	AAS
Emotional Stress	3	7	17/09/2024 16:36	AAS	17/09/2024 17:12	AAS
Follow Aliyev	7	9	17/09/2024 16:20	AAS	17/09/2024 17:15	AAS
Follow Artsun Hovhannisyian	5	6	17/09/2024 16:21	AAS	17/09/2024 17:11	AAS
Follow Pashniyan	3	4	17/09/2024 16:20	AAS	17/09/2024 17:16	AAS
Followed Telegram for News - Azerbaijan	2	3	17/09/2024 17:03	AAS	17/09/2024 17:16	AAS
Followed telegram for News - Armenia	2	5	17/09/2024 17:06	AAS	17/09/2024 17:10	AAS
Incidental News Consumption	5	8	17/09/2024 16:21	AAS	17/09/2024 17:14	AAS
Online Debates with Opposing Side	7	12	17/09/2024 17:05	AAS	17/09/2024 17:16	AAS
Reported not using Legacy Media	7	7	17/09/2024 16:19	AAS	17/09/2024 17:15	AAS
Use Social Media for News	8	16	17/09/2024 16:19	AAS	17/09/2024 17:14	AAS
Trust in Communication	12	33	17/09/2024 13:48	AAS	17/09/2024 15:49	AAS
Decreased in Pashniyan	6	10	17/09/2024 16:18	AAS	17/09/2024 16:52	AAS
Increased in Aliyev	6	10	17/09/2024 16:18	AAS	17/09/2024 16:53	AAS
Things were hidden	5	7	17/09/2024 16:48	AAS	17/09/2024 17:00	AAS
War Discourse	12	43	17/09/2024 13:48	AAS	17/09/2024 16:55	AAS
Changed Opinion or Impacted	6	9	17/09/2024 16:35	AAS	17/09/2024 17:01	AAS
Exposed to Distressing Content	7	14	17/09/2024 16:36	AAS	17/09/2024 17:01	AAS
No Change in Belief	3	4	17/09/2024 16:37	AAS	17/09/2024 17:01	AAS
Proactive	7	8	17/09/2024 16:54	AAS	17/09/2024 17:01	AAS
Reactive	2	2	17/09/2024 16:54	AAS	17/09/2024 16:57	AAS
Reinforced Belief or Opinion	2	3	17/09/2024 16:36	AAS	17/09/2024 16:57	AAS

Transcript AZ-P1

The screenshot displays a qualitative data analysis software interface. The main window is titled "Transcript - AZERBAIJAN AZ-P1" and contains a transcript of an interview. The transcript includes questions from a researcher and responses from a participant (AZ-P1) regarding their use of social media and news consumption. Several parts of the transcript are highlighted in yellow, indicating they have been coded. On the left side, there is a "Codes" panel showing a hierarchical codebook with categories like "Long-term Effects on Peacebuilding and Societal Cohesion" and "Social Media Habits". On the right side, there is a "CODE STRIP" panel showing a vertical bar with colored segments representing the codes applied to different parts of the transcript. Below the transcript, there is a "CODE PANEL" with instructions to drag content into the panel to code it. At the bottom, there is a search bar and a "Code to" field with the placeholder text "Enter code name (CTRL+Q)".

Transcript - AZERBAIJAN AZ-P1

- Age 22
- Sex M
- Education PG Student

Researcher: Just start the recording. OK, now I started the recording. OK, so before we begin with the interview, can you tell me about yourself? Age, education, occupation.

AZ-P1: Yeah, I'm 22 years old. Regarding my education, I finished school here in Baku. I later completed my Bachelor's in International Relations, and I'm currently in my last year of my Master's.

Researcher: OK.

AZ-P1: Yep, that's it.

Researcher: OK. Do you use social media, and which platforms do you use the most?

AZ-P1: Yes, I use a lot of social media. I'm an active user, but I'm not active myself in posting. I use social media mainly to monitor information. Regarding the social media I use most, it's Telegram. It's very popular in my country. I also use X (formerly Twitter) and Instagram. Not sure if YouTube counts as social media, but I'm active there too. In Azerbaijan, Facebook is also very popular, but mainly with older people. For example, my grandparents use Facebook actively, but I rarely check it.

Researcher: OK, that's good. So moving on, I wanted to ask you, do you follow any government accounts or officials on social media?

AZ-P1: Yes.

Researcher: OK.

AZ-P1: I follow the president and the Foreign Minister on X, as well as other governmental agencies. They post all official reports on Telegram. I use other platforms like Instagram only for personal purposes.

Researcher: OK, good. Do you come across news incidentally on these platforms that you use for personal reasons, or does this not happen?

AZ-P1: Yeah, it happens when someone reposts news on Instagram, for example in stories. But the news is usually not new to me because I've already seen it on Telegram or X.

Researcher: OK. Do you think social media is a good way of getting news, or do you think traditional media like newspapers and TV are better?

AZ-P1: I think the important thing is not to focus solely on one or the other. A healthy mix of both is the best way. Personally, I lean more towards modern social media because I believe traditional media like newspapers and especially TV are under government influence. I find online sources a bit more independent.

Researcher: OK, that's good. Have you ever come across posts on social media that changed your opinion or reinforced your existing beliefs?

AZ-P1: It depends. I try to read from different sources to get a variety of viewpoints. For example, when the conflict started, I also subscribed to Armenian social media to get their perspective. But in general, these posts reinforced my existing opinions rather than changing them.

Researcher: So the posts reinforced your opinions but didn't change them entirely?

Appendix VI – Post Wise MCDA Analysis

<p>IA-1 Post 1 of Azerbaijani President Ilham Aliyev on Facebook Date: 18 October 2020 (21st day of the War)</p>	<p>Analysis Brief Description: Image of President in uniform with Azerbaijani Flag in the background with captions</p>
	<p>Translations Left top text in bold capital: Karabakh is Azerbaijan! Middle Text: Ilham Aliyev President of the republic of Azerbaijan, Commander-in-Chief of the armed forces Bottom Left: Department of the Administration of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan</p>
	<p>Visual Details President Aliyev is in uniform, wearing ranks of a general, with a stern expression, looking away from the camera, and the Azerbaijani flag is prominently displayed in the background.</p>
	<p>Engagement Metrics #1 78.3k (likes, reactions, shares, comments) This post falls within a period marked by intense military engagements. The release of this post by official Facebook channel at such a critical juncture in the conflict suggests a deliberate attempt to influence public sentiment and bolster national support.</p>

1. **Context:** The post was published on 18 October 2020, a day marked by significant developments during the Second Nagorno-Karabakh War. This period was crucial as it came immediately after a humanitarian ceasefire, brokered by the OSCE Minsk Group was declared but subsequently violated by both sides (Reuters, 2020: BBC, 2020). Moreover, on the same day, the Azerbaijani MoD and the President announced the capture of the **Khudafarin** bridges (UNESCO World heritage site) and Fuzuli (city named after famous Azerbaijani poet taken by Armenia during First Nagorno-Karabakh War), enhancing its tactical advantages in the region (RIA Novosti 2020: APA 2020). It also likely served to amplify the sense of victory and progress in the war, bolstering public morale immediately following the ceasefire's breakdown. With 78.3k total engagements, this post is the most interacted-with content during the war on President Aliyev's page, showcasing its significant impact and resonance amongst the Azerbaijani audience.

2. Textual Analysis

- a. The post, composed in Azerbaijani without translations, targets the domestic public directly, reinforcing national identity and unity. The choice to use the native language intensifies the message's resonance amidst ongoing hostilities.
- b. **Discursive Script, Type Face, Font and Rhetorical Tools:** The capitalized slogan "KARABAKH IS AZERBAIJAN!", its location in the image and the font size acts as a forceful assertion of territorial claim to Nagorno-Karabakh region, intended to rally public support by invoking strong patriotic feelings and leaving no room for dialogue or opposition. This assertive communication is strategic, aiming to consolidate national morale during a critical phase of the war. Notably absent from the discourse are mentions of the humanitarian aspects such as casualties or the ethnic Armenian presence in the region. This selective omission serves to maintain a narrative focused solely on Azerbaijani victories and rights, thereby avoiding any potential demoralization associated with wartime losses, collateral damage and humanitarian struggle.

3. **Visual Analysis**

- a. **Patriotic Symbolism:** President Aliyev, depicted in military attire (despite being a civilian and politically elected to office) against the backdrop of the Azerbaijani flag, symbolises leadership and the nation's military resolve. This imagery is potent, designed to evoke national pride and a collective resolve to support the war effort.
- b. **Facial Expression and Body Language:** His stern expression and gaze, directed away from the viewer, are emblematic of determination and forward-thinking leadership, reinforcing his assertion as a steadfast commander during turbulent times.

4. **StratCom and IW/IO Aspect:** The omission of details regarding losses or casualties is a tactic of IW. The post focuses solely on the leadership and national strength, maintaining control over the narrative to avoid any negative perceptions or demoralization. This type of information management is designed to counter any Armenian claims and prevent doubts within the Azerbaijani public. The slogan "Karabakh is Azerbaijan" serves as a clear, unambiguous message of sovereignty. This message aligns with the broader strategic goal of legitimising Azerbaijan's territorial claims and rallying public support.

<p>IA-2 Post 2 of Azerbaijani President Ilham Aliyev on Facebook Date: 18 October 2020 (21st day of the War)</p>	<p>Analysis Brief Description: 34 second video of uniformed soldiers with Azerbaijani Flag and Khudafarin Bridges in the background</p>
<p>Eq olsun Azərbaycan xalqına! Qarabağ Azərbaycandır!</p>	<p>Translations</p> <p>Caption Glory to the people of Azerbaijan! Karabakh is Azerbaijan!</p> <p>Soldier Speaking in Azerbaijani Mr. President, Mr. Commander in Chief, in accordance with your order, I am reporting that the Khudafarin Bridges and the surrounding territories were liberated from the occupation. Currently, the Azerbaijani flag is flying here. Long live Azerbaijan, long live the commander in chief, Karabakh is Azerbaijan.</p> <p>Visual Details (3 x frames) A lone soldier in uniform (whilst saluting) is speaking with his face hidden the angle is such that it shows the Khudafarin Bridges and fluttering Azerbaijani flag in the background along with 6 x more soldiers. At 26 second in the video the frame changes to soldiers raising their hands with slogan Karabakh is Azerbaijan! The last frame is of the historic bridge with Azerbaijan flag at the entrance and Iran on the other sides. Chants can be overheard which are a bit unclear.</p> <p>Engagement Metrics #2 56.5k (likes, reactions, shares, comments)</p> <p>This video seems to be an effort to provide documentary evidence on capture of Khudafarin Bridges to counter any negation by Armenia.</p>

1. **Context:** The context of the post is same as the first post and has been presented as documentary evidence regarding capture of Khudafarin Bridges exclusively brought by President Ilham Aliyev.

2. **Textual Analysis**

- a. **Discourse and Use of Rhetoric Tools:** The caption "Glory to the people of Azerbaijan! Karabakh is Azerbaijan!" reinforces territorial integrity rhetoric and enhances nationalistic sentiments behind this slogan that is repeated across multiple posts. This discourse is not only imbued with broader social and cultural ideologies, affirming Azerbaijan's territorial claims but also fails to account for ethnic and humanitarian realities on ground. The soldier's saying "in accordance with your commander-in-chief's order" enhances the image of President Aliyev as a decisive leader who firmly has the military's actions directly under his command. This portrayal is aimed at boosting public confidence in his leadership. Similarly, the repetition of "Karabakh is Azerbaijan" across different mediums (speech and caption) reinforces this as a central nationalistic rhetorical theme for the war.
 - b. **Discursive Scripts and Abstraction:** The speech by the soldier framing Azerbaijani forces as liberators, employs a discursive script that abstracts the realities of the conflict. This abstraction minimizes the focus on casualties, damages, and humanitarian impacts, which are significant yet omitted details, thus maintaining a narrative centered solely on victory and liberation.
3. **Visual Analysis**
- a. **Symbolism of Khudafarin Bridges:** The historical and strategic importance of the Khudafarin Bridges (UNESCO n.d.) is showcased as backdrop in the video giving an overriding effect of meaning to the video. These bridges symbolise cultural heritage and territorial reclaiming of Azerbaijan's historical past that was lost, which is pivotal for seeking support for war as opposed to peace and dialogue.
 - b. **Representational Strategies:** The visual portrayal of the bridges and the placement of the flag symbolises reclaimed sovereignty. The abstraction here is in the visual focus on symbols of victory rather than the realities of the conflict zone, such as the impact on the local population or the landscape.
4. **Textual and Visual Abstraction:** The video abstracts the complex realities of war, focusing instead on symbols of national pride and military success. By not detailing the processes of warfare or its impacts on civilians, the narrative simplifies the conflict to a straightforward story of territorial reclaiming, thus avoiding potential public scrutiny or dampening of morale.
5. **Connecting to Society**
- a. **Micro-level:** Analysis of the actual material forms of communication shows a use of language and visuals to create a narrative focused on unity and victory, omitting any divisive elements.
 - b. **Meso-level:** The video's role within broader kinetic military operations and IW is to bolster national support and justify military actions through simplified, heroic portrayals of the military.
 - c. **Macro-level:** Reflects broader national ideologies and cultural narratives that frame military actions as just and necessary for the restoration of territorial integrity.
6. **StratCom and IW/IO Aspect:** This visual display not only communicates to the domestic publics but also serves as a psychological tactic against opposing forces (discussed as part of MISO in sec [2.1.4](#)), showcasing Azerbaijani military control of vital territory and determination for furthering operations in the region despite repeated calls for a ceasefire. It also counters any Armenian narratives of resistance or control. By showcasing undeniable visual evidence of territorial gain, the post attempts to demoralise the enemy while simultaneously

influencing international observers to accept Azerbaijani victories as legitimate. This tactic of controlling the narrative fits within the broader IW framework of shaping perceptions and undermining the enemy's resolve. The repeated slogan "Karabakh is Azerbaijan" solidifies the long-term objective of territorial reclamation.

<p>IA-3 Post 3 of Azerbaijani President Ilham Aliyev on Facebook Date: 27 September 2020 (1st day of the War)</p>	<p>Analysis Brief Description: Image of President in suit whilst seated with raised fist and quote in Azerbaijani. Snippets of soldiers, missiles and tanks in the background</p>
	<p>Translations Right top text in black: We are on the right path. Our work is the work of justice. We will win! Right top text bolded in blue: Karabakh is ours, Karabakh is Azerbaijan! Right Centre: Ilham Aliyev President of the Republic of Azerbaijan Bottom Right: Department of the Administration of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan</p>
	<p>Visual Details President Aliyev is sitting on a desk, wearing a black suit, blue tie, black analogue watch, with a stern expression and raised right fist, taken as if whilst speaking and looking away from the camera. The quotations marks are bigger than text and in green camouflage colour whilst soldiers, tanks and missiles are seen in the background in grayscale but blurred.</p> <p>Engagement Metrics #3 55.7k (likes, reactions, shares, comments)</p> <p>This post has been made on the first day of the war.</p>

1. **Context:** This post was published on 27 September 2020, immediately after President Aliyev's national address on the first day of the conflict in Nagorno-Karabakh. The speech framed Azerbaijan's military response as a defensive and justifiable act rooted in historical and legal claims. It also sheds light on how the rhetorical slogan of "Karabakh is Azerbaijan!" came into existence as a direct response to Armenian Prime Minister's quote from last year that "Karabakh is Armenia, full stop." (President.az 2020).

2. **Textual Analysis**

- a. The post, composed in Azerbaijani without translations, targets the domestic audience directly, reinforcing national identity and unity. The choice to use the native language typifies the targeted publics.
- b. **Discursive Scripts:** Aliyev's narrative portrays Azerbaijan as defensively reacting to Armenian aggression, effectively mobilising national sentiment however omitting the complex nature of the issue or the fact that the area also has a predominant ethnic Armenia population.
- c. **Dissecting "Karabkah is Azerbaijan!":** This political war slogan, "Karabakh is Azerbaijan," has been prominently featured across the most engaged posts, and it warrants particular attention here as this is the first post during the war where it was used. The timing of its

introduction by the President is strategic, coming after a year's delay following the Armenian Prime Minister's speech in Nagorno-Karabakh, where he declared, "Nagorno-Karabakh is Armenia." This indicates that the slogan was crafted well in advance and deliberately made public at an opportune moment to counter and contrast the Armenian claim. "Karabakh is Azerbaijan!" operates on multiple levels. It employs rhetoric to effectively communicate and persuade, while it functions within a larger discourse to influence and reflect societal beliefs and political ideologies. As a rhetorical tool it was likely used to persuade, unite, and motivate the targeted publics. It resonated emotionally with Azerbaijani's who heard it, invoking feelings of national pride and legitimacy over the territory of Nagorno-Karabakh.

- i. **Asserts Identity and Legitimacy:** The rhetorical aspect is particularly evident in how it asserts identity and legitimacy. The slogan stakes a claim on Nagorno-Karabakh, reinforcing Azerbaijan's territorial rights in the eyes of its citizens and the international community.
- ii. **Mobilises support:** As a call to action, it was designed to galvanize public and political support for Azerbaijan's position and tries to omit the right of self-determination of ethnic Armenian ethnicities in the Nagorno- Karabakh region.
- iii. **Contribution to Discourse:** This slogan contributed to a larger conversation about national identity and sovereignty of Azerbaijan. Its repeated use by the President during his address to media, and citizens was intended to discuss and define the situation in Nagorno-Karabakh in terms of national integrity, reparations for so called Armenian provocations and historical claim. This may have impacted how individuals conceived of and articulated their national identity and geopolitical views influencing public perception and embedding itself into the cultural and social fabric of the nation.
- iv. **StratCom:** The slogan became integral to Azerbaijan's war effort and was likely crafted to achieve strategic political objectives. In hindsight it seems, "**Karabakh is Azerbaijan**", was as a clear, direct message that reinforced national unity and sovereignty, rallying domestic support while presenting a firm, non-negotiable stance to the international community. It mirrors the use of political slogans by China and Russia for territorial and geopolitical issues in its firm and assertive approach for instance "**Crimea is Ours**" became a key part of Russian StratCom efforts, reinforcing national pride and legitimising territorial claims (Associated Press 2024). China's "**One China**" policy asserts its territorial claims over Taiwan and Hong Kong and is consistently used to communicate China's stance on sovereignty to both domestic and global audiences (Chinese Foreign Ministry 2010). During the war, the slogan was used to legitimise Azerbaijan's military actions as part of a broader effort to reclaim what it considers its rightful territory. By simplifying a complex geopolitical issue into an unequivocal declaration, the slogan effectively strengthens President Aliyev's

leadership, both in consolidating post-war control and shaping perceptions on the global stage.

3. **Visual Analysis**

- a. **Patriotic Symbolism:** The visual of President Aliyev with a raised fist, dressed formally, juxtaposed with military imagery in the background, symbolises readiness and determination. The camouflage-coloured quotation marks subtly invoke military themes, enhancing the message of defence and vigilance. It is noteworthy that in this early post, President Aliyev is not depicted in a military uniform, which is uncharacteristic. This portrayal later changed as the war progressed, likely influenced by insights from engagement metrics showing that images of him in uniform garnered more interaction. A likely question for the interview for clarity.
- b. **Visual Semiotics and “Offer” Through Facial Expressions:** The strategic choice of visuals, including the blurred grayscale images of military assets, supports the textual message of readiness and reinforces the seriousness of the Azerbaijani stance. In the image of President Aliyev captured in the moment of speaking, the application of the "offer and demand" concepts articulated by Machin and Mayr is observed. This technique is crucial in how it modulates viewer engagement with the image. Aliyev, depicted while speaking but not looking directly at the camera, embodies the "offer" aspect of this framework. Here, the viewer is invited to contemplate the message and its implications from a reflective distance rather than through direct engagement. This method creates a less confrontational, more thoughtful space for the audience, encouraging them to consider the weight and context of his statements. The choice to use an 'offer' approach rather than 'demand', which would involve direct eye contact and a more immediate emotional connection, subtly enhances the perceived gravity and authority of President Aliyev's message.

4. **Connecting to Society**

- a. **Micro-level:** Immediate symbolic elements of nationalism and justice are communicated through visual and textual rhetoric, focusing on urgency and justification for military engagement.
- b. **Meso-level:** Acts as a rallying call for unity and support, functioning also as a counter-narrative to Armenian claims.
- c. **Macro-level:** Reflects the ongoing dispute over Nagorno-Karabakh, international law, and national identity, reinforcing the legality and righteousness of Azerbaijan's claims.

<p>IA-4 Post 4 of Azerbaijani President Ilham Aliyev on Facebook Date: 28 October 2020 (31st day of the War)</p>	<p>Analysis Brief Description: Image of Turkish and Azerbaijani Flag in full mast with captions</p>
	<p>Translations Top text in White: 29 October, Türkiye Republic Day (Bold) Centre text in Cursive: One nation, two states Centre text in bold: Congratulations Brother People of Türkiye! Bottom Right: Ilham Aliyev President of the Republic of Azerbaijan Bottom left: Department of the Administration of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan</p>
	<p>Visual Details A postcard-style image featuring the flags of Türkiye and Azerbaijan fluttering on flagpoles against a clear blue sky. The sun shines brightly through light white clouds, adding a warm glow to the scene. Captions are placed above the flag centrally and at the bottom of the postcard, President Ilham Aliyev's name is elegantly written in a signature-style font at the bottom right.</p>
<p>Engagement Metrics #4 51.7k (likes, reactions, shares, comments)</p> <p>This post has been made to commemorate the Turkish Republic Day which occurred during the war period.</p>	

1. **Context:** This post was published on 28 October 2020, a day prior to the Turkish Republic Day on 29 October and on the 31st day of the Second Nagorno-Karabakh War. This specific post commemorates, emphasizing the close relationship between Azerbaijan and Türkiye as key allies and during a critical period.

2. **Textual Analysis**

a. The post features the Azerbaijani and Turkish flags, symbolizing the union between the two nations under the slogan "One nation, two states." This expression, frequently used by Aliyev, underscores a shared ethnic and cultural heritage, which has been a cornerstone of his diplomatic efforts to secure regional support and cooperation from Turkic-speaking countries. According to Sahakyan (2022), Aliyev has consistently leveraged the narrative of common Turkic heritage to court sympathy, non-interference, and support from these countries amid regional conflicts. The choice of words like "Congratulations Brother People of Türkiye!" not only celebrates a national day but also emphasises the brotherly relationship. Placing this text centrally in the image draws immediate attention, reinforcing the message of unity.

- b. The use of cursive for the central message adds a personal, heartfelt touch, contrasting with the bold, assertive text that delivers the political message of unity and shared identity. Similarly, the bottom right signatory font name of the President adds a personal touch that draws on his personal relationship with Türkiye. This combination of font styles effectively balances emotional appeal with political assertion.
- c. **Discursive Scripts vis-à-vis Historical Contexts:** President Aliyev's post is a reaffirmation of his view of Azerbaijan's role within the Turkic world, portraying the country as an integral part of this linguistic, cultural and political bloc. This is evident in his speeches where he has often highlighted Azerbaijan's historical and ethnic connections to counter Armenian claims and to solidify regional alliances and counter domestic players such as Russia (Sahakyan 2022). The historical narrative of shared heritage and mutual support has been crucial, particularly in framing the conflict in Nagorno-Karabakh as not only a national struggle but a regional concern involving Türkiye. The continuation of this policy reflects a consistent foreign policy strategy aimed at ensuring support from Türkiye and reinforcing Azerbaijan's position both domestically and internationally. It subtly communicates to both Azerbaijani and Turkish publics that their governments are in close cooperation, potentially facing a common adversary.

3. Visual Analysis

- a. **Visual Semiotics:** The visual portrayal of the flags against a clear blue sky, combined with the celebratory captions, visually reinforces the message of unity and cooperation. The textual content specifically congratulates the people of Türkiye, reinforcing the brotherly bond on a significant national day. The use of warm visual tones and the strategic release timing serve to strengthen diplomatic ties and rally public support.

4. Connecting to Society

- a. **Micro-level:** The post utilizes the imagery flags to convey Turkic brotherhood and affirm support to own and Turkish Public that they are bothers in a shared struggle.
- b. **Meso-level:** Acts as a counter-narrative to global Armenian Diaspora who were active in major cities of the world protesting for a ceasefire and action against President Aliyev by reinforcing alliance with a major NATO Ally on a public platform, influencing public perception and discourse around the Nagorno-Karabakh conflict.
- c. **Macro-level:** The post subtly yet firmly hints at the broader geopolitical dynamics at play during the conflict by showcasing the strong alliance between Azerbaijan and Türkiye. It serves as a strategic signal to regional and global publics that Azerbaijan is not isolated but backed by key regional power. This alliance implies a readiness to support each other, potentially deterring military interventions by other regional players. The celebration of Turkish Republic Day in this context suggests solidarity that extends into military and strategic realms, influencing perceptions and calculations of other potential actors in the region.

<p>IA-5 Post 5 of Azerbaijani President Ilham Aliyev on Facebook Date: 8 Nov 2020 (42nd day of the War)</p>	<p>Analysis Brief Description: Image of X post from Presidents account with Shusha/ Shushi Liberation</p>
	<p>Translations Top text in Blue Bold: DEAR SHUSA, YOU ARE FREE! Centre text in Black: Dear Shusha, we are back! Dear Shusha, we will revive you! Karabakh is ours! Centre text in Blue Bold: KARABAKH IS AZERBAIJAN! Bottom: Department of the Administration of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan</p>
	<p>Visual Details An image of a X post from the official handle of the President with old X logo in the background and</p>
	<p>Engagement Metrics #5 42.6k (likes, reactions, shares, comments)</p> <p>This post was shared on Facebook announcing the capture of psychosocial important town of Shusha/Shushi.</p>

1. **Context:** The post was published on 8th November 2020, a day marked with the most significant development during the Second Nagorno-Karabakh War i.e. capture of Shusha (Shushi in Armenian) by Azerbaijan. According to JAM News (2020), a platform focused on Caucasus it is a town of immense historical, cultural, and strategic importance for both Azerbaijan and Armenia. It has long been a point of contention, particularly in the context of the Nagorno-Karabakh conflict. For Azerbaijan, Shusha is regarded as a symbol of cultural identity and pride, being a historical hub for Azerbaijani music and poetry the town's loss in 1992 during the First Nagorno-Karabakh War to Armenian forces was seen as a major defeat, making its recapture in 2020 a highly symbolic victory for Azerbaijan. The city sits on high ground overlooking Stepanakert (capital of Nagorno-Karabakh) and controls the Lachin Corridor, a vital supply route known as the "road of life" for Nagorno-Karabakh. On 8th November 2020, Azerbaijan President announced the capture of Shusha both through social media and television address. However, this claim was met with immediate denial by Armenia. Armenian officials insisted that fighting in the city was still ongoing. Artsrun Hovhannisyan, from Armenia's defence ministry, stated on Facebook that "the battle in Shushi continues," urging people to believe in Armenian troops (BBC 2020). Before Azerbaijan's official announcement, the Armenian defence ministry spokesperson Shushan Stepanyan also reported on Facebook "the most

ferocious combat" overnight, with significant losses on the Azerbaijani side, including soldiers, tanks, and vehicles (BBC 2020). On the international front, Turkish President Recep Tayyip Erdogan congratulated Azerbaijan on the recapture of Shusha, calling it a sign that "the rest of the occupied lands will be liberated soon too" (BBC 2020). On 7th November, Erdogan reinforced this stance during a conversation with Russian President Vladimir Putin, stressing that Armenia must withdraw from Azerbaijani lands and be "convinced to sit down at the negotiating table" (BBC 2020).

2. Textual Analysis

- a. **Discourse, Transitivity, and Modality:** The post's central discourse revolves around victory, liberation, and national identity. The phrase "DEAR SHUSA, YOU ARE FREE!" evokes emotional resonance, transforming Shusha into a personalized symbol of Azerbaijan's historical and cultural past. The discourse positions Azerbaijan as the righteous victor, reclaiming its cultural heritage and territory from Armenian control. Additionally, the post's message echoes earlier Azerbaijani claims that "KARABAKH IS AZERBAIJAN," tying it to a longstanding political slogan. This continuity in messaging creates a strong sense of ideological consistency and reinforces Azerbaijan's official narrative over the course of the war. Phrases like "we are back" and "we will revive you" place Azerbaijan in the role of a proactive, righteous force. This reinforces the power dynamic, where Azerbaijan is the liberator and Armenia is implicitly cast as the occupier. The transitivity here highlights who holds the power (Azerbaijan) and who is being acted upon (Shusha and, by extension, Armenia). The post uses definitive, high-modality language. Expressions such as "you are free" and "we are back" signal certainty and resolve, leaving no room for ambiguity about the state of Shusha. This reflects the Azerbaijani government's confidence in their military success and their rejection of any conflicting narratives, particularly from Armenian sources.
- b. **Discursive Scripts:** The post follows a discursive script of **liberation and restoration**. The actors (Azerbaijan and its military) are portrayed as liberators, reclaiming Shusha from occupation. The outcome (liberation and revival of Shusha) presents a positive, forward-looking narrative that emphasizes national pride. This script downplays the complexities of war and instead centres the discourse on the inevitability of justice and restoration, reinforcing ideological unity.

3. Visual Analysis

- a. The image lacks intricate visuals, instead emphasizing text, which becomes the focal point. The lack of embellishment ensures that the viewer's attention is squarely on the announcement of Shusha's liberation, reinforcing the post's simplicity and directness which could also be attributed towards the speed of announcement rather than making complex visuals. The use of bold text in blue for the most critical statements ("DEAR SHUSA, YOU ARE FREE!" and "KARABAKH IS AZERBAIJAN!") aligns with the seriousness and importance

of the victory. The absence of complex imagery allows the text itself to act as the primary signifier of victory.

4. **StratCom and IW/IO Aspect:** The timing of this post serves multiple strategic and IW functions. It is meant to signal to both Azerbaijani publics and the international community that Azerbaijan has decisively captured a significant cultural and military target. Implicitly, the post aims to demoralise Armenian forces and publics by confirming Shusha’s capture while discouraging any potential military intervention from regional players by reinforcing Azerbaijan’s dominance in the conflict. The combination of text and image in this post works cohesively to deliver a straightforward, authoritative yet timely message. The lack of complex visual elements directs focus on the textual proclamation, ensuring that the main message—Shusha’s capture—is clear and unambiguous.

<p>NP-1 Post 1 of Armenian Prime Minister Nikol Pashinyan on Facebook Date: 10 Nov 2020 (44th day of the War)</p>	<p>Analysis Brief Description: Facebook Live Video of 21 mins 46 sec titled “Why and who is to blame?” in Armenian</p>
	<p>Translation</p> <p>We are happy, not because we had any other choice in the current situation, but because no other option was available. I plan to provide more detailed information about why, what was the reason, and I will speak about the events of the last month, in detail. I cannot do it now for one simple reason: the process of ceasing military operations is still ongoing. If I reveal certain things now, it could endanger lives. Of course, if I disclose certain facts, many things will become clear to people, but I cannot say them now because it would risk the lives of others. I cannot say those now, in order not to put some people’s lives in danger. Today, those who are causing destruction, they are backstabbing our boys who are standing in the frontline positions. Incidentally, it has been suggested by certain famous circles that there are contradictions between the army and political leadership. They claim that efforts are being made to protect the army from leadership interference.</p> <p>Yes, today, there is an opposition politician who has demanded my resignation. It was just the other day that this politician abandoned his position in Shushi and fled. He, with shoulder strap of a general. Today he claims that they are standing by the army, then why did he run away? I am certain that among today’s organisers of the disorder. I know that there are people whose intentions are honest and fair. I know there are also relatives of our fallen brothers among them. I have said, and will continue to say, that I kneel before these people — their relatives, their mothers, fathers, sisters, wives, and children. If I must speak a single sentence, it is that I realise I am obligated not to say certain things today.</p> <p>However, I will say this: today, I was told that some of those orchestrating these protests include oligarchs and criminal groups. These are the people who, for 20 years, have stolen from soldiers, who, for 20 years, have stolen from the army, who, for 20 years, have evaded taxes, yet now they stand here, speaking of a nation and treason. What are these people doing in Yerevan? Haven’t they heard the calls of the president of Artsakh? Haven’t they heard about the calls about Shushi being in danger? Haven’t they heard the screams of help? What are these people doing in Yerevan wearing camouflage? Can someone explain to me? This is a convenient moment for them to protect what they have looted. Today, do you know why they can easily enter here and there and demolish whatever they want? Because all our police and security forces, including the National Security Service, are on the front lines. Even my son is in the front lines, even my wife is in the front lines, my wife is in the front lines, and I am proud of that. But I understand that I must provide a detailed explanation, which I am prepared to give today, but why am I not? Because we have an issue with informational dissonance. During military conditions, every</p>

word and sentence has an impact on military activities, direct impact. And that's the reason for dissonance, and we have understood this, and you should understand this too. Because a Facebook post or a statement reaches the frontlines, and the enemy, very quickly. This is why I cannot say everything I want to say at this moment. But I want you to understand that the decision we made was firstly based on the military situation analysis provided by those most knowledgeable about the military situation. We need to understand one thing, our glorious army fought against terrorists, the second army of NATO, and Azerbaijan. Why were we unable to achieve a different outcome for today's paper having a different content? Because for 25 years, we sat around tables, drinking toasts to our soldiers, and that vodka, wine, the bread put on the table, some people, this is about some people, was bought with stolen money. And we knew about this, while sitting around the table, we knew that it was bought with stolen money, that bread, but we ate with appetite, drank with joy, drank a toast for our soldiers standing on our feet, yes, and how did we feed the soldier? We kept our soldiers equipped with 1980s weapons and placed our hope in a negotiation process, where we would lie ourselves around (uses slang word derived from Russian 'krutit,' meaning to twist or deceive). Well, five years you lie yourself around (same slang word), six years you lie yourself around (same strong slang word), ten years you lie yourself around (same slang word), fifteen years you lie yourself around (same slang word), how long can you lie yourself around (same slang word)? Eventually, the end comes. And when you don't think about the end, and we all did not think about that end. Those who should have thought about it considering their positions, did not, and we all failed to realise we were heading towards this day.

I was aware. Because from the first day I was informed about the content of negotiations, moreover, about the negotiation content in a situation, where all the resources for lying ourselves around (same slang word) were already consumed. And by the way, there are people from these circles among those causing destruction. It was all consumed. And what have I done? Instead of taking the negotiation heritage and saying that I will realise this, I tried to prepare for this day, doing everything possible within two and a half years. Our army fought honourably for over 44 days, enduring countless hardships. I repeat, I kneel before the families of our martyrs — their mothers, fathers, sisters, brothers, wives, and children. I ask for their forgiveness for not being able to continue the work of their fallen loved ones properly. Not only the fallen ones of this war, but ones before this as well. But we made this decision, considering the current military situation and the potential future continuation. I ask all citizens not to fall for the provocations of criminal groups. I was informed, they were some famous political party circles, for example, there is a person in that circle who, according to the framework of a legal case, owes the state eighty billions drams, which is almost one hundred seventy five million dollars, which is more than the money gathered by the All Armenian Fund, which should have been paid over the years into the state budget, at least the sixty percent of it, or half of it, because the other half is fines, which must have turned into a weapon, which must have turned into equipment, which must have turned into science, which must have turned into UAVs, and so on. And these people cause destruction today, to restore their rights to loot. They have been gnashing their teeth for two and a half years, asking themselves, how this happened? How did we lose our opportunities to loot?

Yes, I admit we haven't done enough in the last two years to return stolen funds, but we've tried to address corruption legally. For 25 years, Armenian laws were written to protect corruption and the corrupted system. This is the truth. And I apologise that I cannot discuss everything in detail right now because the situation on the front is unstable. It is important to do so, so that we don't harm. I understand, emotions are running high, and they must be expressed, but there will be time for detailed conversations in the future. No one who bears responsibility, including myself, will run from it.

I call on all citizens of Armenia not to give in to provocations. I know that my responses today are incomplete, as I said in the beginning, because there are many details I cannot yet reveal. After the situation is stabilised in a week, I will tell everything. But I want you to know and be sure that my government and I have done everything possible to avoid this outcome. Why didn't it work? That is the key question, and we will have that detailed conversation when the time is right, in order to understand the full context.

	<p>Thanks for following, thanks to those who were believing, thanks to those who do not believe, but I have only one expectation, that these people will listen, and will draw conclusions as a result.</p> <p>Today, we have squads of governors standing on the frontlines, some of them enduring the fever, and you know why they are standing while having a fever? affected with coronavirus, and so on, because the people causing the disorder have refused to take their place on the frontlines. How long can one stand in the frontline? Ten days, fifteen days, but there is a way and order to this, isn't there? This is the whole issue.</p> <p>I may return to the live broadcast later if I have more to say. I call on everyone not to give in to provocations, and I assure you that those responsible for today's crimes will be held accountable. Don't doubt. We will not allow chaos in the Republic of Armenia, nor will we let deserters return to deliver opposition speeches. Those who go take pictures on Facebook, but later when there is a military situation, they leave it all and run away quickly, moreover without any additional difficulties. They come to Yerevan very fast to deliver opposition speeches.</p> <p>That is, it. I love and respect all of you, and I am proud to serve you. Please do not doubt for a second that anything has been done against my service duties towards you. Do not doubt for a second. I will definitely prove it. You will decide whether I did prove or not. And once again, I kneel before all our martyrs and their mothers, fathers, sisters, wives, children, relatives. Thank you</p>
	<p style="text-align: center;">Visual Details</p> <p>One frame throughout where the president is in a suit looking facing down at the camera</p>
	<p style="text-align: center;">Engagement Metrics #1</p> <p style="text-align: center;">194.2k (likes, reactions, shares, comments)</p> <p>This post was shared on Facebook announcing that the war is over, and a ceasefire agreement has been signed with Azerbaijan mediated by Russia apparently addressing why and who is to blame for this situation.</p>

1. **Context:** On 10 November 2020, Armenia, Azerbaijan, and Russia signed a peace agreement to end the six-week conflict over Nagorno-Karabakh. The deal marked a significant defeat for Armenia, as Azerbaijan retained control of areas it captured during the conflict, including the key town of Shusha. Armenian Prime Minister Nikol Pashinyan described the agreement as "incredibly painful" for both him and the Armenian people, and protests erupted in Yerevan, where angry crowds stormed the parliament and government buildings, accusing the government of betrayal (BBC 2020).

2. Textual Analysis

- a. **Discourse:** Pashinyan's speech remains centred around justifying the ceasefire and placing the decision within the broader context of internal corruption, military necessity, and national sacrifice. The speech constructs a discourse of inevitability, where the ceasefire was the only available option. Pashinyan frames himself as a leader who, despite recognising the nation's sacrifices, has decided based on military analysis and pragmatism. This shifts the narrative away from defeat towards justified survival.
- b. **Discursive Scripts:** The speech introduces a stronger focus on blame towards corrupt elites and their role in undermining Armenia's strength. This script reinforces a hero-villain binary: Pashinyan and the soldiers are depicted as the moral defenders of the nation, while oligarchs and opposition figures are cast as the internal enemies responsible for Armenia's weakened position. This mirrors a common discursive script in times of national crisis, where blame is attributed to internal betrayal as much as external threats.

- c. **Transitivity Analysis:** Pashinyan positions himself and the soldiers as active agents, while framing the corrupt oligarchs as responsible for Armenia's downfall. He shifts the agency of failure onto these internal actors, suggesting that their decades of stealing and undermining the system led to the current military outcome. By contrast, Pashinyan portrays the army and himself as acting in the best interests of the nation, highlighting the martyrs' sacrifices and framing the ceasefire as a necessary choice for survival.
 - d. **Modality:** The speech is delivered with high modality, as Pashinyan asserts the certainty of his decisions and the necessity of the ceasefire. The use of definitive language ("we are happy," "we had no other choice") alongside phrases like "I cannot say them now" conveys both authority and restraint, as Pashinyan implies that his leadership remains the only logical solution to the current crisis.
 - e. **Narrative Analysis:** The narrative structure of the speech is divided into two parts: justification and deflection. The first part of the narrative establishes the justification for the ceasefire, with Pashinyan explaining that there was no other option due to the military situation. The second part shifts to deflection, where he criticises past corruption, criminal elements, and oligarchs, placing the blame for Armenia's current vulnerabilities on decades of mismanagement. By doing so, he shapes a collective narrative in which the loss is part of a larger story of systemic failure, not the result of decisions made during the war. This narrative aims to create a sense of communal responsibility while exonerating his administration from direct blame for the loss.
 - f. **Lexical Choice:** Pashinyan's lexical choices are deliberate and emotionally charged. Words like "martyrs," "sacrifice," and "glorious army" invoke a sense of national pride and honour. The introduction of slang (krutit) and informal language reflects Pashinyan's attempt to connect with ordinary citizens, distancing himself from the corrupt elite. By using strong, colloquial terms, Pashinyan taps into the popular frustration with the oligarchs and those who profited from the nation's struggles. The repeated use of the word signals his disgust with the political and military establishment, framing himself as a man of the people. This choice of language amplifies the emotional appeal of his message.
3. **Visual Analysis:** The production of this video, with a straightforward, sombre tone, highlights the urgency and gravity of the moment. Broadcasting the message on Facebook ensures it reaches a broad audience both in Armenia and among the Armenian diasporas. The distribution through social media allows for real-time engagement, reflected in the high number of interactions.
 4. **Critical Pragmatics:** Pashinyan's speech is carefully timed to defuse tensions in the wake of the ceasefire announcement. His emphasis on unity and calm is meant to prevent unrest, as he warns against giving in to provocations by criminal elements. His mention of oligarchs and past corruption serves to shift some of the blame away from his administration and onto others, positioning him as someone who fought hard to avoid this outcome but was ultimately limited by systemic issues. By acknowledging the pain and sacrifice of the Armenian people, Pashinyan attempts to control the public narrative and prevent dissent.
5. **StratCom and IW/IO Aspect:** This post helps control the narrative of defeat, ensuring that Pashinyan's version of events dominates the public sphere. By focusing on the martyrs' sacrifices, he shifts the conversation away from tactical defeat and toward the moral and emotional aspects of the conflict. His warnings against

provocations pre-empt unrest, framing potential dissent as destructive to national unity. He positions himself as the responsible leader who made the difficult choice to save lives while discrediting political opponents and oligarchs as corrupt forces that undermined Armenia's strength.

<p>NP-2 Post 2 of Armenian Prime Minister Nikol Pashinyan on Facebook Date: 16 Oct 2020 (20th Day of the War)</p>	<p>Analysis Brief Description: Video of 10 mins 23 seconds with caption in Armenian</p>
<p>Ելույթ ունեցա հայրենիքի պաշտպանությանը զինվորագրված գումարտակի ...</p>	<p>Translation</p> <p>Caption: Today I gave a speech in front of the battalion enlisted for the defence of the motherland. To enlist for the defence of the homeland, apply to your military commissariat and remember that the future of Armenia depends on one person and that one person is you.</p> <p>Speech: Soldiers of the Armenian army, I salute you, brothers. I would have liked to stand before you today and say that stability and peace have been restored in our homeland, that the motherland no longer needs your military service, and that it now requires your civilian service once again. But unfortunately, that is not true. Today, we are here, and you are here, because our motherland still needs your service, and the service of each and every one of us. We are in a situation today where each of us must forget our previous civilian roles, and as a nation, we must all enlist in the defence of our homeland. But I want you to understand clearly what you are doing by being hundreds of kilometres away from your homes, your children, and your loved ones. You will be standing in defence of your children, your families, and your homes. You might look around and not recognise any familiar tree or bush, but in reality, you will be standing at the doors of your children's bedrooms, at the entrance to your own homes, and in front of your children's schools. Where you go, you will be defending the nation to ensure that you don't have to defend your own homes and bedrooms later. You will prevent the enemy from setting foot on our land. I myself stood in the very position you stand in now, in the spring of 2016. Back then, I made the decision to volunteer and defend the homeland. It happened in an instant—when I woke up one morning and saw my daughter, less than a year old, sleeping peacefully. I decided that I would go to protect her peaceful sleep, and if necessary, I would give my life for the homeland so that my child, my neighbour's child, my friend's child, and my brother's child could live and win. We will not surrender. We will not retreat. We will not give up in disgrace. We will stand in defence of our homeland. Let's also reflect on the global situation. Many people ask whether we have friends in the world. I assure you, yes, we have friends. But those friends will not make decisions for us. They will, however, support the decisions we make. If we choose defeat, they will respect that choice. But if we choose victory, they will</p>

Երկր ռևեցա հայրենիքի պաշտպանությանը զինվորագրված գումարտակի ...

Երկր ռևեցա հայրենիքի պաշտպանությանը զինվորագրված գումարտակի ...

support our decision to win. I am convinced, as a people with thousands of years of history, that we have the ability to make difficult decisions, and the hardest of those decisions is to win.

I ask you; I urge you; I demand of you: leave this place with victory in your hearts, victory in your minds, and victory in your souls. Remember that you are fighting to protect your homes, your families, your identity, your dignity, and your manhood—and you will win. We will win. This nation will continue to exist on this planet because we are here today thanks to the victories that our ancestors won 1,000 years ago. We fought, we endured, and we survived. Our very existence today is the result of their sacrifice. We are not only singing for today, but also for the future of our nation. And you are the ones who bear this mission. You carry this legacy. I want to say once again that the future of Armenia, the future of the Armenian people, depends on one person—and that person is you. If each of us realises that the future of Armenia depends on one individual, and that individual is himself, then we will be invincible. And we will win.

I love you all. I am proud of each and every one of you. I bow before all of you. I believe in you, I believe in each of you, that you are heroes. I believe that you will defend the future of your children and our children with dignity. And so, long live freedom! Long live the Republic of Armenia! Long live the Republic of Artsakh! Long live the Armenian diaspora! Long live the Armenian army! And long live the victory of the Armenian people!

Visual Details (5 x Basic Frames)

- Frame 1:** A soldier brings the column of soldiers to attention (at night in an open space) and salutes the Prime Minister in suit.
- Frame 2,3:** Prime Minister addresses the soldiers from two angles one zoomed on his face and one from a distance behind the soldiers (showing their point of view).
- Frame 4:** Soldiers cheering and chanting.
- Frame 5:** Prime Minister meets the soldiers and fist bumps them.
- Frame 6:** Logo of Prime Minister of the Republic of Armenia

Engagement Metrics #2

165.4k (likes, reactions, shares, comments)

This video was shared on Facebook in attempt to increase volunteering for the war.

1. **Context:** This post was made halfway through the war, during a period of heavy fighting and several failed ceasefire attempts by OSCE Minsk group.

2. **Textual Analysis**

a. **Discourse:** The speech delivered by Pashinyan is deeply rooted in nationalism, emphasising sacrifice and duty. It paints a vivid picture of collective responsibility where each citizen is positioned as a critical agent in defending the homeland. Pashinyan frames the war as a personal battle for each Armenian citizen, urging them to enlist and defend their homes, children, and future. His narrative invokes the historical resilience of

the Armenian people, linking the current conflict to centuries of struggles for survival. This discourse fosters national unity and positions Armenia's plight as a continuation of its historical fight for freedom.

- b. **Discursive Scripts:** The speech follows a discursive script of mobilisation. Pashinyan emphasises that the war is not just a military conflict but a moral and existential battle. By focusing on the individual responsibility of every citizen, he creates a narrative that suggests victory is possible through collective effort. The repeated personal references, such as his own experiences of volunteering to defend his daughter's peaceful sleep, function as a script of shared struggle, reinforcing solidarity between Pashinyan and the soldiers.
 - c. **Modality:** The speech is characterised by high modality, with Pashinyan speaking in definitive terms. He uses assertive language to inspire confidence, leaving little room for doubt about the necessity of action. The modality signals that the outcome of the war depends entirely on individual contributions, creating a sense of urgency. Phrases like "we will not surrender," and "you will win," reinforce a certainty of success, aimed at uplifting the morale of the soldiers and the general population.
 - d. **Narrative Analysis and Lexical Choice:** The speech follows a mobilisation narrative, with soldiers and citizens framed as heroes defending the future. The repeated use of words like "victory," "duty," and "sacrifice" creates a narrative of moral obligation and heroism, presenting the conflict as a battle for survival rather than just a territorial dispute. Pashinyan's lexical choices further enforce a sense of identity and pride, with references to "manhood," "family," and "heritage" appealing to deeply ingrained cultural values. The reference to the future of Armenia depending on each individual elevates the personal stakes for every listener.
3. **Visual Analysis:** The video frames Pashinyan addressing the soldiers at night, symbolising seriousness and urgency. The backdrop of a night sky and the soldiers standing in formation reflect the military context and the gravity of the situation. The choice of night-time visuals, along with Pashinyan's formal attire, contributes to an image of solemn duty and leadership. The close-up shots of Pashinyan's face as he speaks, paired with wider shots showing the soldiers' point of view, create a sense of camaraderie and unity. The soldiers' cheers in response to his speech, along with the fist bump exchange, visually symbolise solidarity and motivation. The mix of zoomed-in frames and distant shots further communicates intimacy and power in equal measure. The visual narrative reinforces the mobilisation theme. Pashinyan is shown directly engaging with the soldiers, standing among them as one of their own, rather than distanced as a detached leader. The narrative of heroism and duty is furthered by the soldiers' chants and cheers, which visually convey their enthusiasm and readiness for the task ahead. The visuals of Pashinyan leading the charge add to the narrative of leadership in crisis.
 4. **Multimodal Cohesion:** The text and visuals in this post are tightly integrated, creating a cohesive message of national unity, personal responsibility, and mobilisation. The formal setting of the speech, coupled with the night-time military formation, complements the tone of urgency and duty conveyed through Pashinyan's words. The fist bumps and soldier chants at the end of the video visually represent the solidarity and shared mission that Pashinyan advocates for throughout the speech. The use of close-ups during emotional parts of the speech aligns the visual intensity with the emotional weight of the narrative.
 5. **Critical Pragmatics:** This post serves as a rallying call for national mobilisation, aimed at encouraging volunteers to enlist and defend the country. By emphasising the personal stakes of the conflict—such as protecting one's family and future—Pashinyan appeals to the emotions and moral obligations of his audience. The speech is strategically timed to reinforce national unity as the war drags on, and the immediacy of the threat is conveyed through both the text and visuals. Pashinyan's emphasis on personal responsibility highlights the agency of the individual in shaping the nation's future, serving to mobilise and motivate soldiers and civilians alike.
 6. **StratCom and IW/IO Aspect:** This post exemplifies StratCom, with Pashinyan delivering an impassioned plea to the Armenian people to mobilise in the defence of the homeland. The speech evokes national pride and personal responsibility, tapping into historical narratives of sacrifice and resilience. By framing the war as a moral battle for survival, Pashinyan seeks to maintain public morale and increase volunteerism, reinforcing the idea that victory is achievable if every citizen takes up their duty. His use of emotive language and personal anecdotes

strengthens the emotional connection with the audience, making the call to action immediate and impactful. From an Information Warfare (IW) perspective, the post controls the narrative of the war by framing the conflict as a defensive struggle for survival. Pashinyan shifts focus away from potential military setbacks, emphasising the moral high ground of defending one’s family and nation. By positioning everyone as a critical agent in the war effort, he boosts morale and counters defeatist sentiment. The visual and textual emphasis on unity and readiness helps maintain a sense of purpose and resolve, ensuring that the Armenian population remains committed to the war effort despite the challenges.

<p>NP-3, Post 3 of Armenian Prime Minister Nikol Pashinyan on Facebook Date: 5 Oct 2020 (9th day of the War)</p>	<p>Analysis Brief Description: 5 x images of 2 soldiers firing artillery rounds</p>
	<p>Translation of Armenian Caption: Let me bear your pain, you are winners.</p> <p>Visual Details Image 1: Soldier-1 takes a selfie in uniform on the battlefield, holding the firing cord of a field artillery gun. The gun position is visible in the background, displaying the military setting. Image 2: Soldier-2 is captured in a close-up shot, gently smiling whilst wearing a strapless helmet. His calm and happy expression is in focus, with the outside of the gun position in the background. Image 3: Soldier-2 is seen covering his ears with his hands, preparing for the imminent firing as Soldier-1 prepares to fire the artillery round. Images 4 and 5: Two different angles of the artillery gun firing, with the muzzle flash vividly captured as the round is discharged.</p> <p>Engagement Metrics #3 163.7k (likes, reactions, shares, comments)</p> <p>This post was shared on the ninth day of the war showing the life of soldiers in the field.</p>

1. **Context:** On 4 October 2020, Azerbaijani President Ilham Aliyev announced the capture of several villages in the Jabrayil region, signalling a significant territorial gain for Azerbaijan in the ongoing Nagorno-Karabakh conflict (Almasdar News 2020). The following day, on 5 October 2020, Armenian forces confirmed a partial tactical retreat from some areas, presenting it as a strategic repositioning rather than a defeat. (Almasdar News 2020). Prime Minister Nikol Pashinyan’s post, shared on the same day, aimed to reassure the Armenian public, showing calm and composed soldiers in action. The message highlighted resilience and confidence, countering concerns about the retreat while projecting an image of determined resistance.

2. **Textual Analysis**

- a. **Discourse:** The textual component of this post embodies a discourse of resilience and leadership. The phrase, "Let me bear your pain, you are winners," conveys solidarity between the prime minister and the soldiers. Pashinyan positions himself as empathetic and supportive, indicating a deep connection with the military personnel on the front lines. This discourse aligns with the broader nationalistic narrative of standing strong in the face of adversity, where the government is portrayed as being emotionally and morally connected to the struggles of its people.
- b. **Discursive Scripts and Abstraction:** The text frames the soldiers as active agents in the conflict, emphasising their role as heroes who endure pain but are destined for victory. The mention of "pain" acknowledges the hardships of war, but immediately shifts focus to triumph by labelling them as "winners." This script reinforces an ideology of heroism and sacrifice for a just cause, positioning Armenian soldiers as central to the national defence effort.
- c. **Transitivity Analysis:** In this context, Pashinyan assumes the role of a caretaker, offering to bear the burden of the soldiers' pain. However, the soldiers remain the active agents of the actions, specifically in their role as combatants. The soldiers are not portrayed as passive victims but as resilient actors who are actively contributing to the national struggle. This reinforces their responsibility and agency in the ongoing conflict.
- d. **Modality and Evaluation:** The modality of this text is high, with an expression of certainty and confidence. Pashinyan refers to the soldiers as "winners" despite the ongoing war, conveying an unwavering belief in the inevitability of their success. This confidence serves to reassure the domestic audience that despite the pain and sacrifices, victory is assured. The use of "Let me bear your pain" also implies a strong sense of obligation on Pashinyan's part, enhancing the bond between the leader and the soldiers.
- e. **Narrative and Lexical Choice:** The narrative created by this text highlights personal sacrifice and victory through endurance. The phrase "winners" carries connotations of triumph and success, reinforcing the idea that Armenian soldiers are fighting not just to survive but to win. The word "pain" adds an emotional layer, acknowledging the hardships while redirecting focus towards the expected positive outcome. This emotive language is designed to generate public empathy and support for the soldiers.

3. Visual Analysis

- a. The five images chosen for the post carry significant semiotic meaning. The juxtaposition of selfies with scenes of military action humanises the soldiers while maintaining their role as active combatants. The smiling face of Soldier-2 in one image, for example, introduces an unexpected sense of calm in the chaos of war, presenting an image of controlled bravery. The images of the artillery gun firing capture moments of action and agency, visually representing the soldiers' active role in defending the nation.
 - b. The visuals carry high modality in their clear and vivid portrayal of the battlefield, reinforcing the realism and authenticity of the situation. The images do not attempt to glorify or dramatize the conflict but show the soldiers in everyday actions, thus lending credibility and truth to the narrative of resilience and confidence.
 - c. The visuals follow a script of calmness under pressure. Soldier-1, smiling and preparing to fire the artillery gun, reflects a narrative of confidence and control. The imagery portrays the soldiers as individuals, but with a calm and composed demeanour, suggesting that they are not overwhelmed by the intensity of the war. This reinforces the idea of professionalism and resilience among the Armenian forces.
4. **Multimodal Cohesion:** The cohesion between the text and visuals is strong, with both elements working together to reinforce a narrative of calmness, strength, and resilience. The empathetic tone of the caption pairs well with the humanising images of the soldiers, particularly the selfie, which offers a relatable and accessible image of combatants. The text promises victory and relief from pain, while the visuals show the soldiers actively contributing to that victory with confidence and determination. The overall message is one of solidarity, endurance, and control.
 5. **Critical Pragmatics:** The context in which this post was shared—on the ninth day of the war—makes it clear that the purpose of the post was to rally support and maintain morale both among the soldiers and the public. The post is designed to demonstrate that despite the hardships of war, the Armenian soldiers are maintaining composure, and the leadership is standing by them, willing to bear the weight of the struggle. The inclusion of

smiling soldiers taking selfies in the midst of battle serves to counteract fear or doubt, projecting an image of normalcy and control despite the intensity of the situation.

- IW/IO Aspect:** This post also serves IW function by countering Azerbaijani narratives of victory and portraying Armenian soldiers as resilient and in control, despite territorial losses. The use of composed imagery and messaging reinforces the psychological resilience of Armenian forces, helping to shape both domestic and international perceptions of Armenian strength and determination in the face of adversity.

<p>NP-4 Post 4 of Armenian Prime Minister Nikol Pashinyan on Facebook Date: 10 Oct 2020 (14th Day of the War)</p>	<p>Analysis Brief Description: 60 x images of the Armenian Diaspora rallies in major western cities</p>
<p> 10 October 2020</p> <p>Այս օրերին աշխարհի հայությունը ցույց է տալիս համախմբվածության ուժը: Այս շարժումը պետք է զրավիչ դարձնել նաև այլ ազգերի ներկայացուցիչների համար՝ ուլջեր դեմ են բռնությանը, կոռուպցիային, ահաբեկչությանը եւ ձգտում են արդարության, ազատության եւ սիրո հաղթանակին:</p> <p>Արցախը պետք է դառնա համաշխարհային արդարության խորհրդանիշ:</p> <p>Աշխարհը պետք է ճանաչի Արցախի ինքնորոշման իրավունքը: Եթե դա չեն անում կառավարություններն ու խորհրդարանները, դա կարող են անել ժողովուրդները, անհատները, կազմակերպությունները:</p> <p>Սա պետք է դառնա այդպիսի անհատներին, ժողովուրդներին, կազմակերպություններին միավորող համաշխարհային շարժում:</p> <p>These days, Armenians across the world show strength of unity. This movement must also be made attractive to the representatives of other nations who are against violence, corruption, terrorism, and pursue victory of justice, freedom, and love.</p> <p>Artsakh must become a symbol of world justice.</p> <p>The world must recognize the right to self-determination of Artsakh. If governments and parliaments do not do that, peoples, individuals, organizations can do it.</p> <p>This movement should become a global movement uniting such individuals, peoples and organizations.</p>	<p>Caption in English and Armenian: These days, Armenians across the world show strength of unity. This movement must also be made attractive to the representatives of other nations who are against violence, corruption, terrorism, and pursue victory of justice, freedom, and love. Artsakh must become a symbol of world justice. The world must recognize the right to self-determination of Artsakh. If governments and parliaments do not do that, peoples, individuals, organizations can do it. This movement should become a global movement uniting such individuals, peoples and organizations.</p>
	<p>Visual Details 60 x images of the Armenian Diaspora protesting against the war in prominent cities, featuring placards, posters, and Armenian flags. Each image captures key moments from the protests, with the location of the city captioned in the top left corner.</p>
	<p>Engagement Metrics #4 144.2k (likes, reactions, shares, comments) This post was shared on the 14th day of the war showing the protests and rallies held across western prominent cities by Armenian Diaspora.</p>

- Context:** Global protests were organised by the Armenian diaspora around this time in major Western cities during the Nagorno-Karabakh conflict. These protests aimed to raise awareness and advocate for Nagorno-Karabakh (Artsakh as per Armenian perspective) right to self-determination, pushing for international recognition and support. With an estimated 7 million Armenians living worldwide, the diaspora has been a significant asset for Armenia’s international advocacy (Office of the High Commissioner for Diaspora Affairs n.d.). These protests were part of a broader effort to generate global attention and put pressure on foreign

governments especially western powers to recognise the conflict as a struggle for human rights and justice in Nagorno-Karabakh and bring an end to the war (Collard 2020).

2. Textual Analysis

- a. **Discourse:** The discourse in this post revolves around global unity and the fight for justice. By framing the protests as part of a larger movement against violence, terrorism, and corruption, Pashinyan is broadening the issue beyond Armenia's territorial struggle. The reference to "victory of justice, freedom, and love" places the Nagorno-Karabakh conflict in a broader moral context, aligning it with global values. This language is designed to attract support not only from the Armenian diaspora but also from international audiences who identify with these principles.
- b. **Discursive Scripts and Abstraction:** The discursive script positions the Armenian diaspora as active agents in the fight for recognition. The post highlights the diaspora's role in promoting Artsakh's right to self-determination, reinforcing a narrative of global advocacy. The call for individuals, peoples, and organisations to join the movement shows the expansion of agency, inviting non-Armenians to participate in this global cause, thereby shifting the discourse from a localised conflict to a global movement.

3. Visual Analysis

- a. The Armenian flags and protest placards in the images symbolise unity, resistance, and advocacy. The recurring presence of flags visually reinforces the sense of national identity, while the placards highlight key messages that frame the conflict within a global moral context. The images are highly detailed and vibrant, conveying a high level of realism and immediacy, suggesting that these protests are ongoing, and that the movement is actively growing.

4. Connecting Text to Society

- a. **Micro Level:** The text in the caption serves as a direct call to action for Armenian diaspora and presenting the struggle as a globally supported cause.
 - b. **Meso Level:** The production of this post, with multiple images of protests from around the world, showcases a highly organised effort to highlight the diaspora's global presence. The distribution on social media, particularly Facebook, is meant to amplify the reach of this message, ensuring it is consumed not only by the Armenian community but by international observers. The consumption of this post, especially among diaspora members, reinforces their role in the fight for recognition, while appealing to non-Armenians who might sympathise with global movements for justice.
 - c. **Macro Level:** At the macro level, the post ties into broader international discussions of self-determination and human rights. By framing Nagorno-Karabakh's right to self-determination as a global issue, Prime Minister Pashinyan aligns Armenia's cause with international principles of justice and human rights. This helps legitimise Armenia's position on the global stage and seeks to gain international recognition and support.
5. **Critical Pragmatics:** The timing of this post is key, as it was shared on the 14th day of the war when international pressure and visibility were becoming increasingly important for Armenia. By showing the diaspora actively protesting, Prime Minister Pashinyan aimed to generate global awareness and mobilise further support, signalling to foreign governments that the conflict had widespread backing from citizens in their own countries. The call for action at the individual and organisational level reflects a pragmatic understanding that formal diplomatic channels may not move quickly enough, thus encouraging grassroots movements to play a pivotal role.
6. **StratCom and IW/IO Aspect:** Prime Minister Pashinyan's post effectively utilises StratCom by showcasing the global protests of the Armenian diaspora to emphasise the widespread international support for Armenia's cause in Nagorno-Karabakh. By highlighting the unity of Armenians worldwide, the post strategically frames the conflict as a global movement for justice, appealing to broader international values of human rights and self-determination. This approach is reinforced by the call for non-Armenians to join the movement, expanding its reach beyond the Armenian community. From an IW perspective, the post counters any narrative of Armenian isolation by projecting a strong, organised international backing. It aims to mobilise public opinion and pressure

foreign governments to support Artsakh’s right to self-determination, while also challenging Azerbaijan’s narrative by demonstrating that the Armenian cause has significant global advocacy.

<p>NP-5 Post 5 of Armenian Prime Minister Nikol Pashinyan on Facebook Date: 14 Oct 2020 (18th day of the War)</p>	<p>Analysis Brief Description: Image of the Armenian Prime Minister, dressed in a black suit, shown prostrating in his office. The image includes a caption in Armenian.</p>
	<p>Translation Caption in Armenian: I mourn for our valiant martyrs who defended the motherland with their lives, the right of their people to live, defended our identity, dignity and future. And I bow before all our victims, martyrs, their families, their parents and especially mothers, and I consider their loss my loss, my personal loss, my family's loss.</p>
	<p>Visual Details The Prime Minister is depicted prostrating in his office, with the Armenian flag in the background. The setting is grand, featuring two polished marble pillars, a fine mosaic carpet, and dark wooden wall fittings, adding to the dignified atmosphere.</p>
	<p>Engagement Metrics #5 163.7k (likes, reactions, shares, comments) This post was shared on the 18th day of the war commemorating the fallen soldiers.</p>

1. **Context:** Same as [NP-2](#).
2. **Textual Analysis**
 - a. **Discourse:** The discourse in this post is centred around mourning, dignity, and sacrifice. The language is solemn and emotional, designed to resonate deeply with families who have lost loved ones and the broader Armenian public. Pashinyan’s message connects national identity with the personal sacrifices of the soldiers, making the loss of life part of a collective national tragedy. The discourse reflects the ideals of heroism and dignity in death, reinforcing the moral high ground of Armenia’s fight in the war.
3. **Discursive Scripts:** This post follows the discursive script of a shared national loss, where the leader not only mourns alongside the nation but expresses a personal connection to the fallen soldiers and their families. Pashinyan frames the soldiers as defenders of the motherland, embodying dignity, identity, and the right to live. The script positions the loss of life as a sacrifice for the greater good of the nation, creating a sense of communal suffering that binds the country together in the face of adversity.
4. **Visual Analysis**
 - a. The act of prostration is a powerful visual symbol of humility and respect, while the Armenian flag in the background links the Prime Minister’s personal mourning to the nation’s collective identity. The formal, dignified setting reflects the gravity of the moment, while the polished marble pillars and dark wooden wall fittings convey a sense of tradition and solemnity.

- b. The image carries a high level of modality, with its clear, well-lit, and detailed portrayal of the Prime Minister's office. The setting and imagery are designed to communicate authenticity and seriousness, ensuring that the audience perceives the moment as genuine and profound.

5. **Connecting Text to Society**

- a. **Micro Level:** The use of first-person language ("I mourn," "I bow," "I consider their loss my loss") creates a direct and personal connection between Pashinyan and the families of the fallen soldiers. The solemn tone and repeated use of the word "loss" reinforce the weight of the sacrifices made. The image of Pashinyan prostrating adds a layer of visual solemnity to the text. The formal setting, including the Armenian flag in the background, emphasises the official and dignified nature of the post. The dark suit and subdued colours reflect the mourning atmosphere, while the polished, grand setting symbolises the gravity of the occasion.
 - b. **Meso Level:** This post was likely carefully curated to reflect national mourning. The production of this post emphasises the personal connection between Pashinyan and the Armenian public, portraying him as not just a leader but someone who shares in the country's grief. The distribution on Facebook ensures widespread visibility, reaching both the domestic audience and the Armenian diaspora, creating a unified message of mourning. The consumption of this post is aimed at both comforting the families of the fallen and reinforcing national unity through a collective expression of grief.
 - c. **Macro Level:** At the macro level, this post reflects broader social and cultural norms of honouring the dead during times of conflict. By positioning the fallen soldiers as defenders of national identity and dignity, Pashinyan ties their sacrifices to the broader nationalistic narrative of the Nagorno-Karabakh conflict. The language of shared grief and loss serves to legitimise the sacrifices made during the war, framing them as necessary for the survival and future of Armenia.
6. **Multimodal Cohesion:** The text and visuals work together seamlessly to create a unified message of mourning and respect. The sombre tone of the text aligns with the dignified and solemn visuals, reinforcing the idea of sacrifice and national mourning. Together, the text and image create a compelling narrative of shared loss, where the Prime Minister is not just a leader but a member of the national family, mourning alongside his people.
7. **Critical Pragmatics:** The text and visuals work together seamlessly to create a unified message of mourning and respect. The sombre tone of the text aligns with the dignified and solemn visuals, reinforcing the idea of sacrifice and national mourning. Together, the text and image create a compelling narrative of shared loss, where the Prime Minister is not just a leader but a member of the national family, mourning alongside his people.
8. **StratCom and IW/IO Aspect:** This post is a strong example of StratCom, where Prime Minister Pashinyan through his communication shows himself personally with the families of fallen soldiers to reinforce national unity. By portraying the soldiers' deaths as noble sacrifices for the country's identity and future, Pashinyan strengthens public support for the war effort and maintains morale. The use of solemn visuals and personal language emphasises collective grief, positioning the conflict as a fight for national survival. From an IW perspective, this post controls the narrative by framing the losses as honourable and necessary, countering potential demoralisation. By presenting these sacrifices in a dignified and respectful manner, Pashinyan ensures that the public views the soldiers' deaths as integral to the larger cause of Armenia's future, helping to maintain resilience in the face of adversity.

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